
LuSEE-Night Preliminary Design Report

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

LuSEE-Night is a project to investigate the feasibility of measuring the fundamental physics processes occurring during the cosmic Dark Ages using instrumentation on the lunar surface. The "Dark Ages" refers to the cosmic era between the last scattering of the cosmic microwave background and the time when the first stars and galaxies formed. Only cold, non-luminous hydrogen gas existed during this epoch, and so it has been largely unexplored and remains one of the least constrained frontiers of modern cosmology. The community has therefore shown increasing interest in developing an experimental Dark Ages program based on observations of the hyperfine 21-cm transition of neutral hydrogen, seen against the backlight of the CMB. The global (sky-averaged) spectrum of the redshifted 21cm line is sensitive to the temperature and ionization state of the hydrogen gas and provides a tomographic probe of the thermal history of the early universe, possibly including signatures of new physics beyond the standard model. The recent National Academies ASTRO2020 Panel on Cosmology rated this technique as "...both the discovery area for the next decade and the likely future technique for measuring the initial conditions of the universe in the decades to follow" ([1], p.258).

This document describes a design for a detector that will establish the feasibility of measuring the 21-cm absorption trough in the CMB global spectrum predicted to lie in the highly redshifted frequency range between 4 and 40 MHz. Because of strong terrestrial RFI and ionospheric distortions, this signal cannot be observed from the Earth or from Earth orbit. The detector will therefore be stationed on the lunar surface, on the radio-quiet far side facing away from Earth. To avoid interference from solar RF emissions, observation will take place during the lunar night.

The LuSEE-Night instrument is a radio frequency spectrometer consisting of a set of antennas, analog and digital signal processing electronics, and the necessary mechanical, thermal, communications, and power delivery hardware to support reliable operation on the lunar surface. Four horizontal monopole antennas are arranged to produce wide, zenith-directed beams. As the Moon rotates, the instrument's wide field of view traverses a path covering much of the sky, providing coarse angular resolution. The combination of polarization, spectral, and angular information will provide for offline deconvolution to separate the cosmological signal from much stronger foreground components. Together, the antenna and preamplifier electronics are designed to be close to sky-noise limited over the 1 - 50 MHz band. Each antenna's output is processed by a signal chain having analog amplification and filtering, and Nyquist-rate digitization. The four channels of digitized data are fed to an FPGA-based "software-defined radio" signal processor that computes auto- and cross-correlation spectra and stores data in nonvolatile memory. Since LuSEE-Night will never be in view of the Earth, the data will be sent back to the science operations center via periodic contact with an orbiting relay satellite (not part of the LuSEE-Night project).

The design of the LuSEE-Night instrument leverages space-proven technology developed for NASA's STEREO/WAVES [2] and Parker Solar Probe/FIELDS [3] missions. These experiments included antennas and spectrometers similar to those needed for this project. To reduce risk and facilitate a highly compressed development schedule, we will adapt the antenna, spectrometer, and power conditioning elements of these predecessor experiments for LuSEE-Night.

For LuSEE-Night to survive on the lunar surface, detailed attention is paid to thermal management. The length of the lunar cycle (29.5 Earth days) and its lack of atmosphere results in extreme surface temperature swings – from 95K at lunar midnight to +390K at lunar noon. The instrument enclosure thus needs both a heat rejection path during the day and a tightly thermally isolated envelope at night. NASA partners will be responsible for these elements of LuSEE-Night. Radiation levels are

non-negligible and COTS electronics will be selected from qualified manufacturers or by upsampling COTS parts. Since radioisotope-based generators will not be permitted, LuSEE-Night will be powered by a battery array for the periods of nighttime observing, which will recharge from a photovoltaic array during each succeeding lunar day.

LuSEE-Night additionally includes a digital calibration source in orbit around the moon. The digital calibrator source emits a known coded broadband signal that can be detected in cross-correlation even when buried in the bright emissions from the Milky Way galaxy and enables precision understanding of the beam pattern and its chromaticity.

The LuSEE-Night instrument consists of elements provided by two DOE labs (Brookhaven and Lawrence Berkeley) and NASA's Space Sciences Laboratory at UC Berkeley. Once assembled and tested, it will be flown to the Moon as a payload element of NASA's Commercial Lunar Payload Services CS3 mission, scheduled for launch in early 2025. Upon successful landing and commissioning, LuSEE-Night will begin operations and expects to deliver about 2-6 GB of science and telemetry data every lunar cycle with nominal mission duration of 18 lunar cycles. Equipment survival could enable a potentially longer mission.

1 SCIENCE

1.1 DARK AGES COSMOLOGY

The Cosmic Microwave Background is the main pillar of modern observational cosmology. This is radiation released some 400 thousand years after the Big Bang, when the primordial cosmic plasma made of mostly hydrogen and helium atoms immersed in the sea of photons and electrons cools to the temperature at which photons and matter decouple: matter forms neutral hydrogen atoms and light begins to propagate freely through the universe. This same radiation, redshifted to mm wavelengths, is observed today as the CMB. The large distance lever arm of the CMB, and our ability to model the physics using easily solvable linear equations, makes it a truly unique probe, upon which most of the other cosmological probes build upon.

The hundred million years following the formation of the CMB, corresponding to redshifts between $z \sim 1100$ and $z \sim 30$, are referred to as the **Dark Ages**. This is the epoch after the primeval fireball has cooled down, but before the first stars lit up. At these redshifts, cosmological density fluctuations can be directly probed with the 21 cm line whose physics is completely described by well-understood processes governed by gravity, atomic physics, and thermodynamics [4]. Once the first stars begin to form at $z \sim 30$, their emitted radiation alters the neutral hydrogen in the intergalactic medium, which depends on complex non-linear astrophysics, and disallows the first-principles understanding present at previous times. Therefore, the Dark Ages present an incredible opportunity in terms of precision cosmology, essentially free of astrophysical complexity. However, precisely for the same reason, this epoch is not amenable to the traditional surveys used to probe the evolved Universe, which use galaxies or other objects to trace the underlying distribution of matter.

Redshifted 21-cm emission and absorption from neutral hydrogen is **the single known method** that allows, at least in principle, observations of this period in the evolution of the Universe. This emission corresponds to the energy difference between the spins of the electron and proton that are aligned or not aligned in a hydrogen atom. There is no other line in its vicinity and hence it is not easily confused with electromagnetic interaction by other species. The theory of 21 cm emission from the Dark Ages is very well understood: fluctuations in 21 cm emission are sourced by density, temperature and velocity perturbations, which we can calculate from first principles at those redshifts. This has been recognized decades ago [5], but the practicalities are daunting, starting with the fact that the signal is redshifted outside the windows of atmospheric transparency that would allow observations from the Earth's surface. This measurement would, however, provide the holy grail of cosmology, as it probes the same linear physics as CMB experiments, while mapping more three-dimensional Fourier modes of the density field than available in large-scale redshift surveys. This signal has the potential to enable the ultimate sensitivity to the cosmological parameters, including those from early-universe inflation and primordial gravitational waves. However, we have to recognize that this is the end-game that will take decades to develop, should it even prove technically possible.

Another analogy with the CMB is appropriate. The CMB monopole signal (i.e. the CMB itself) was discovered in 1964 by Arno Penzias and Robert Woodrow Wilson for which they received the Nobel Prize in 1978. This discovery was extremely informative and has established the Big Bang theory as the leading cosmological theory. It took another 26 years for the COBE Satellite to measure *spatial fluctuations* in the CMB, for which George Smoot received the Nobel Prize in 2006. It is notable that George Smoot was an employee of the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, illustrating the great science that can be achieved when DOE and NASA collaborate. The discovery of fluctuations and their subsequent characterization with the WMAP and Planck missions cemented the CMB as

the cornerstone of cosmological observations. A similar timeline could play out with the Dark Ages 21-cm signal. A detection of the monopole is feasible over the next decade and it would take several decades to work our way towards detection of fluctuations. This would be the arc of a long-term science roadmap towards a new and truly transformational tool for cosmology.

Figure 1.1: The predicted 21 cm monopole intensity through cosmic times (plot from [6] in turn adapted from [7]). The lunar farside is the best site to attempt to measure the *Dark Ages dip*, at around $\nu \sim 20$ MHz or equivalently redshift $z \sim 80$.

The first stage in the program is the detection of the Dark Ages monopole. Shown in Figure 1.1, this signal is a small dip in the observed radiation intensity as a function of frequency integrated over the entire celestial sphere. It will be detected by measuring a broad absorption trough centered at around 20 MHz. Because the physics is linear and well-understood, we have a prediction for the size and shape of this effect. Any deviation from this template would have immediate and profound implications for fundamental physics. Because there are no astrophysical uncertainties, it would necessarily imply new physics once the possible sources of systematics have been ruled out. The most plausible way of changing the shape and amplitude of this trough is through heating and cooling of the cosmic medium through non-standard processes. Therefore, the Dark Ages dip in the monopole of radiation is the **cosmic calorimeter** that can measure the net energy flows in the baryon fluid. A large number of theoretical proposals exist which can cause deviations from the simplest predictions [8], including dark matter-baryon scattering [9, 10, 11, 12], millicharged dark matter [13, 14], dark-matter annihilation [15, 16], primordial black holes [17], axions [18], neutrino decay, charge sequestration [19], quark nuggets, dark photons [20], interacting dark energy [21] and even a drift in the value of the fundamental constants [22].¹ These are all topics of high interest to the DOE HEP community and can be probed from the lunar surface within the next decade independently of astrophysics. Detection of the monopole would require setting up a low-resolution and high-efficiency radio telescope either stationary on the far side of the Moon or in orbit around the Moon.² Similar to the evolution of the CMB, the path towards detection of the fluctuations would involve working over several decades with radio telescopes of increasing size and complexity on the lunar farside. These instruments will require significant infrastructural development on the Moon, including the provision of power and significant bandwidth. With such a futuristic apparatus, we can hope to detect fluctuations across the sky and thus open a new era of

¹See Astro2020 Decadal Survey Submission [8].

²A detection of the monopole at 78 MHz, arising from the era of the first stars rather than the Dark Ages, has recently been claimed by an Earth-bound experiment [23], demonstrating the feasibility of such detections with current technology.

observational cosmology a few decades from now.

As a general probe, a Dark Ages Lunar experiment would be able to probe primordial fluctuations deep into what were linear scales at the time, but which are deep in the non-linear regime today and whose information has been largely lost. This is illustrated in Figure 1.2 which shows how this probe would be transformation both in terms of scales that are probed as well as raw sensitivity. For more information see the science described in the Snowmass paper [24] – while that paper is focused on more near term probes, a Dark Ages experiment would perform much of the same science with orders of magnitude more sensitivity.

Figure 1.2: Figure demonstrating the current state of the inference on the linear power spectrum and a possible reach of the Future Lunar experiment. Adapted from https://github.com/marius311/mpk_compilation/.

1.2 RADIO SKY AT 1-50MHZ

Following the visionary path set up in the previous section will require a decade long program of investment. To enable sound investment, we need to start with a modest experiment that tests the basic assumptions about the observability of the signal. There are three main issues that make this effort challenging:

- **Earth’s Ionosphere and RFI.** The ionosphere severely limits our ability to observe the low-frequency sky from the ground, by modulating signals in frequency as a function of time of arrival that renders any precision observations impossible from the Earth. This motivates observations from the Moon or deep space. Additionally, other sources of low-frequency emission from the Earth, including both man-made (radio emissions as well as sparking in electrical and mechanical devices, and similar sources) and meteorological means that observations from the Moon are best made from its far side.
- **Foregrounds.** Other astrophysical sources of radio emission produce signals which are orders of magnitude stronger. These signals can be distinguished from the signal of interest by their frequency and spatial response differences; however any instrumental leakage from the

foreground modes into the signal region through imperfect calibration needs to be understood at the parts-per-million (ppm) level. This requires exquisite calibration, which is particularly difficult from the lunar surface, given our limited control over the observatory. In addition to the very loud galactic emission, the Sun and planets are also loud emitters, whose emission however is characterized by time and frequency variability.

- **Low frequencies.** The radio emission at the frequencies of interest has very long wavelengths that require physically large devices. The wavelength at 10 MHz corresponds to 30m radiation and natural antennas for observations would need to be appropriately sized. Therefore we are mostly working in the short antenna limits with corresponding hits on the antenna sensitivity.

The long term goal is to develop technology that will allow us to make high-precision and high-sensitivity observations from the far side of the moon. This is currently an almost entirely unexplored territory.

Figure 1.3: Figure demonstrating the radio quietness of the far side of the lunar surface as measured by the RAE-2 experiment [25]. "Immersion" and "Emersion" correspond to the satellite orbiting to behind the Moon where it is shielded from solar and Earth's emission.

The most relevant radio astronomy observations to date were done by the RAE-2 satellite [25], [26], and ground-based measurements by Cane et al. [27]. In Figure 1.3 we show the result from RAE-2 that confirms the expectation that terrestrial RFI in this frequency range is strongly attenuated when the view towards Earth is blocked by the Moon. These early studies also provided models of the galactic foreground spectra, shown in Fig. 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Galactic foreground emission (from [26] [27]). The LuSEE-Night frequency range is shown shaded.

1.3 LUSEE-NIGHT SCIENCE OBJECTIVES

The primary goals of LuSEE-Night are to:

1. **Establish the Lunar surface as a viable observatory for low-frequency radio astronomy.** There are multiple unknowns regarding observations from the lunar surface. These include the effects of the regolith, constancy of electromagnetic shielding in the presence of magnetic fields, and unknown level of transient phenomena associated with micrometeoritic impacts as well as lunar plasma effects.
2. **Perform the most sensitive observations of the radio sky at 1-50MHz.** This frequency regime is motivated by the fact that any observations around the target frequency of ~ 17 MHz will require sufficient lever arm on both sides of the dark ages dip to enable separating the dip from the broadband emission. We aim to make measurements with absolute flux calibration better than 20% across our frequency range.
3. **Quantify the systematic effects affecting global spectrum measurement accuracy, and investigate methods to mitigate them.** We will develop models, test procedures and analysis methods to extract the frequency dependence of the antenna beam pattern and signal chain gain, both pre-flight and during operation.
4. **Constrain the presence of a non-smooth monopole component at the 10^{-3} level compared to foregrounds.** This is about 3 order of magnitude below the required sensitivity to measure the Dark Ages dip, but will nevertheless be the strongest constraint to date, paving the road for more sensitive future experimental designs.

The system presented in the subsequent sections will have sufficient sensitivity and systematics control to achieve these science goals.

2 INSTRUMENT

2.1 DESIGN OVERVIEW

The LuSEE-Night instrument is a radio frequency spectrometer consisting of a set of antennas, signal processing electronics, power and thermal management hardware, and a communications link for control and data transfer (Fig. 2.1). An orbiting calibration source is planned. The instrument payload will be developed by DOE and NASA partner organizations and delivered to a Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) provider for integration with a lander and transport to the lunar far side. Radio observations will take place primarily during the lunar night when strong solar emissions are blocked. Data acquired during night observations will be stored to nonvolatile memory and transmitted (via a relay satellite, see Section 3.5) to the mission operations center during the lunar day. We are designing for a mission duration of 18 lunations with a threshold plan of one full lunation.

Figure 2.1: LuSEE-Night instrument: conceptual block diagram, constraints, and operations concept.

Designing the instrument to deliver the key performance goals of LuSEE-Night means that three significant challenges must be addressed:

- **Surviving the thermal and radiation environment.** The tidal locking of the Moon’s rotation to the Earth and its lack of atmosphere result in extreme excursions of the surface temperature from night to day. To prevent overheating or overcooling of the electronics, LuSEE-Night needs

special thermal accommodations. Radiation levels are several times higher than those in low Earth orbit, and components must be sourced from qualified parts lists or qualified by the project.

- **Powering during periods of darkness.** With CLPS prohibitions on radioisotope thermal generators (RTGs), the only source of nighttime power will be batteries that are charged during the lunar day by a photovoltaic array. Battery mass constraints thus limit the allowable power consumption of the spectrometer.
- **Self-generated radio frequency interference (RFI).** LuSEE-Night's spectrometer will be designed to be sensitive to extremely low levels of radiofrequency power. During night operation all inadvertent sources of RF emission will need to be carefully managed. For example, all lander equipment will be totally shut down after commissioning; the RF front end amplifiers will be shielded; and all switching circuitry in the instrument will be slaved to a master clock.

The major elements of the LuSEE-Night instrument are shown in block diagram form in Figure 2.2. The core electronics will be assembled as a sandwich of four "slices" referred to as the Main Electronics Crate (MEC). The slices include the spectrometer board, a Command and Data Handling Board (C&DH), and two slices for managing power delivery. The final slice houses the communications User Terminal and S-band transceiver. A 8225 W-hr lithium battery is integrated with the MEC to form the Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA). The IEA will be housed in an outer enclosure providing thermal isolation during the night and heat rejection during the lunar day, see Section 3.3. Mounted to the top of the outer enclosure are:

- four deployable monopole antennas riding on an azimuthal rotation stage, each with its own RF preamplifier (Section 3.1);
- a photovoltaic solar array for daytime powering and battery charging (Section 3.4);
- an S-band patch antenna for communication to the relay satellite (Section 3.5).

Figure 2.2: Electronic interfaces: Primary power (grey), Secondary power (black), data and command (blue), RF (magenta).

The major instrument subsystems will be discussed in detail in Section 3.

2.2 OVERALL SYSTEM SPECIFICATION

2.2.1 Key Performance Parameters

The science goals of LuSEE-Night can be met if the system satisfies the parameters listed in Table 2.1, derived as follows:

1. A monopole pair can be operated as a pseudo-dipole and will measure flux and one component of polarization. A second monopole pair will increase the effective aperture and provide a simultaneous measure of the orthogonal polarization.
2. System bandwidth is chosen to include the region where the Dark Ages absorption feature is predicted to exist.
3. Threshold sensitivity corresponds ensures that the dominant galaxy signal will be measured with signal-to-noise above unity in a single spectrometer integration period.
4. Refers to the number of frequency bins computed by the spectrometer. Higher granularity will improve RFI mitigation algorithms.

5. The power consumed by the instrument during night operations. This is dictated by the maximum battery mass.
6. Refers to that portion of the total payload mass (not-to-exceed value of 100kg) allocated to the subsystems provided by the DOE MIE project.

2.2.2 Verification

KPPs 1,5, and 6 can be verified by trivial measurements. The system sensitivity is influenced by features of the lunar surface environment that cannot be replicated in an Earth-based laboratory. The verification of KPP-3 will therefore be based on a set of measurements (feedpoint impedance of the antenna and equivalent input voltage noise density of the front end electronics) and simulations (3D electromagnetic field solvers with appropriate lunar environment parameters) which are input to the sensitivity model. KPP-4 is a parameter in the spectrometer firmware and achieving the objective will depend on the efficiency of the FPGA code.

A preliminary estimate of feasibility is given in Section 2.3.2. In the final design phase more refined models and measurements will be developed and analyzed, and together with component-level measurements will provide validation of this requirement.

KPP#	Parameter	Threshold	Objective	Unit
1	Number of monopole antennas	2	4	-
2	System bandwidth	1-20	0.2 - 50	MHz
3	System sensitivity (1s integration, 1024 bins)	$< 10^{-20}$	$< 10^{-21}$	W/m ² /Hz/sr
4	Frequency resolution	400	75	kHz
5	Power consumption (avg during obs)	17	12.5	W
6	Mass (DOE MIE subsystems)	85	75	kg

Table 2.1: Key Performance Parameters.

2.3 DESIGN TRADEOFFS AND PERFORMANCE ESTIMATE

2.3.1 The Design Tradeoffs

LuSEE-Night design is heavily constrained by the aggressive timeline, which requires strong use of heritage technology. We have therefore chosen very early on to use the STACER dipole antennas and optimized the instrument for science return within these constraints. Here the basic parameters that we have control over is the number and lengths of antennas, their height above ground (within realistic lander designs) and their actuations. In this section we will briefly qualitatively review the trade-offs and then proceed to demonstrate that our adopted design meets the science objectives set in Section 1.3.

Through careful considerations of analytic model of a dipole in space as well as quantitative work using EM field simulations, we have identified the main antenna design trade-offs. These will be discussed in more detail in the Section 3.1, but we qualitatively summarize them here as introduction to the sensitivity forecast.

The first trade-off is in the antenna length. Longer antennas are more sensitive. They have both a higher radiation resistance, which means a higher voltage spectral density at the same antenna load. They also have a higher capacitive impedance whose effect goes in the opposite direction

(see discussion around Eq. 2.4 below), but the overall effect is that the longer antennas are more sensitive. On the other hand, longer antennas have both more chromaticity in antenna coupling to preamplifier as well as more chromatic beam response on the sky, especially above any resonant feature that comes into our observing band. While the chromaticity in antenna coupling can in principle be calibrated out, the presence of resonances make it particularly sensitive to details of electromagnetically relevant local features like detail of regolith, conductive structures on the lander, etc., which is undesirable. The chromaticity of the beam, is even more undesirable. If a certain source is in the beam at some frequencies, but not in the others, this can produce frequency dependent response, which can be confused with any non-smooth signal of cosmological origin. This can be fatal in separating of foregrounds and any signal of interest. Through both qualitative and quantitative studies we have settled on 3m long stacers.

The second trade-off is between antennas of the same lengths vs antennas of different lengths. Antennas configurations in which two orthogonal pseudo-dipole have different lengths have several attractive properties. Different antenna lengths have different beam shapes improving our ability to deconvolve the measured signal into a low-resolution map of the sky. With a rotational stages, we can rotate the system by 90 degrees and thus flip the arrangement of lengths, allowing us to reconstruct all relative arrangements between antennas lengths and sky structures. Since different antenna lengths also couple differently to the ground, having a pair of different lengths help us constrain the ground properties and its effect on the beam. On the other hand, four antennas of the same length have a different set of desirable properties. By using rotational stage to rotate the 4 antennas in what is nominally the same array allows us to very sensitively separate the effects of sky signals from the effects of the analog chain and regolith. It also allows a simplifies constructions of the model of foregrounds, since there are fewer possible antenna combinations to model. Finally, it allows for better understood measurements of polarization components, since the crossed-dipole used is symmetric. We have chosen to adopt a symmetric configuration with all antennas of the same length.

The third trade-off is in antenna height with respect to the ground. The closer antennas are to the ground, the more antenna couples to the ground, decreasing sensitivity to sky signals. However, at antenna heights above a few meters, resonances are excited between the antennas and the ground, leading to considerably worse beam and coupling chromaticities. Our simulations indicated optimal antenna height to be 3 ± 0.5 m.

The fourth trade-off is in actuation possibilities. We have considered several actuation possibilities, including rotation in both azimuth (rotation of the antenna system around the vertical axis) and elevation (antenna angle with respect to the vertical). The obvious downside of actuation is that it increases the overall system complexity and weight. A more subtle downside is that antenna system reconfigurations are only possible during day-time, implying a small number of possible configurations, 18 in the nominal mission duration. With two degrees of freedom, the sampling of the configuration space becomes quite limited. Moreover, some configurations have lower sensitivity, which needs to be traded against any usefulness in beam change. We have chosen to descope the elevation actuation which was present in the conceptual design to have a system that is simpler from mechanical and modelling point of view.

A final tradeoff study concerns optimization of the first transistor in the preamplifier. In general, the preamp input capacitance should be as low as possible to minimize signal loss via capacitive coupling. To first order, both the input capacitance and the transconductance of a JFET transistor proportional to its gate width, hence reducing the gate width to obtain a better impedance match entails an increase in the equivalent voltage noise density, as well as a reduction in the device's

gain-bandwidth product. Further complicating the choice of input transistor is the need to operate at low bias currents to stay within the subsystem power budget, and the low availability and high cost of space-qualified parts. The relevant part selection is discussed in Section 3.2.2.

The careful considerations of these trade-offs will be described in more technical detail in Section 3. In the next section we will demonstrate that our fiducial design meets our design goals.

2.3.2 Instrument Sensitivity

In our system, the signal from each of the 4 monopole antennas is separately amplified and then all possible auto and cross correlations are measured in the spectrometer. While our preliminary sensitivity calculations were based on pseudo-dipole, our current calculations are based on the actual electronic design of the instrument. The instrument is composed of four monopoles, which are coupled and amplified independently. They can be fed into spectrometer as formed pseudo-dipoles or individually. Since 4 auto and 6 cross-correlations fully describe all quadratic components of the correlation matrix, the sensitivity does not depend on this choice: one can always rotate to the desired basis. We will therefore proceed by calculating signal-to-noise from 4 monopole auto-correlations and all opposite-antenna cross-correlations. Certain signal combinations will be very useful for systematic checks but they carry limited signal-to-noise for primary science.

In this and the following section we forecast noise-levels assuming observations at 10° south of the lunar equator at longitude 180° , although the details of the landing site do not affect the results strongly. Integration time was assumed to be equivalent of 18 lunations with 14 earth days of useful data per lunation and 100% spectrometer efficiency. Lowering the spectrometer duty cycle is our dominant approach for keeping the power consumption within its allocation. In this scenario noise levels will increase inversely proportional to the square root of the effective integration time.

We start by considering the auto-correlation signal. The flux density received by each antenna (in $\text{W}/\text{m}^2/\text{Hz}$) at wavelength λ is

$$S_\nu = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2k_B}{\lambda^2} \right) \left[\int_{\Omega} T_{\text{sky}}(\theta, \phi, \nu) B(\theta, \phi, \nu) d\Omega + f_{\text{ground}} T_{\text{ground}} \right], \quad (2.1)$$

where $B(\theta, \phi, \nu)$ is the beam profile and the factor $1/2$ is due to the fact that the dipole only responds to one polarization. We assume the sky signal to be unpolarized and hence B is the response of the antenna to the I polarization component. The f_{ground} described the fraction of the beam that is coupled to the ground. The beam integrates to unity at each frequency, so in the limit of the uniform sky, we have

$$S_\nu = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2k_B}{\lambda^2} \right) [f_{\text{sky}} T_{\text{sky}} + f_{\text{ground}} T_{\text{ground}}], \quad (2.2)$$

with $f_{\text{ground}} + f_{\text{sky}} = 1$. The shape of the beam response B is derived from electromagnetic simulations, with details given in Section 3.1. Note that in the presence of a regolith, there is no beam at elevations below horizon and f_{ground} is derived through consideration of energy conservation. We model the voltage spectral density in units of V^2/Hz received at the spectrometer in auto-correlation as

$$P = 4S_\nu \lambda^2 R_{\text{rad}} \Gamma_{\text{VD}}^2 + e_n^2, \quad (2.3)$$

where radiation resistance is assumed to be the real part of the antenna impedance ($R_{\text{rad}} = \text{Re}(Z_{\text{ant}})$), since ohmic losses in the antenna can be shown to be negligibly small. Factor Γ_{VD}

Figure 2.3: Sensitivity plot for galactic signal from simulations described in the text. The green line shows the mean antenna signal, while the band encompasses minimum and maximum received. The blue line is the signal that one would see if the sky was uniform (pure monopole) with the Novaco-Brown spectrum. The difference between the green and blue lines are due mostly because our experiment does not sample the sky uniformly, but at low frequency end are dominated by the known discrepancy between ULSA sky model and Novaco-Brown measurement. The plot on the left show the monopole auto-correlation while the plots on the right show our two cross-correlation products. There are two kinds of cross-correlations: the opposite pairs of monopoles and the L-shape (90° relatively oriented) pairs of monopole. In cross-correlation both real and imaginary products are measured. A uniform sky will not produce an imaginary part correlation and the observed mean of imaginary mode is very close to zero, which will be an excellent cross-check of our systematics. The dotted grey line corresponds to the instantaneous signal-to-noise assuming $4 \text{ nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$ noise figure, while the solid grey line is the noise level per bin after one second assuming 1024 bins in 0-50MHz band. Finally, the dashed gray line shows the power from $10^{-21} \text{ W/m}^2/\text{Hz}/\text{sr}$ uniform sky load confirming that we fulfill our Key Performance Parameter #3.

describes the coupling of the antenna to the amplifier in the "voltage divider" picture with

$$\Gamma_{\text{VD}} = \left| \frac{Z_{\text{rec}}}{Z_{\text{ant}} + Z_{\text{rec}}} \right|, \quad (2.4)$$

where Z_{ant} and Z_{rec} are the antenna and receiver complex impedances. Antenna complex impedance is a product of EM simulation. The receiver complex impedance is assumed to be dominated by the capacitances of the front-end JFET and stray capacitances added in parallel $Z_{\text{rec}} = (i\omega(C_{\text{stray}} + C_{\text{iss}}))^{-1}$. The real part of receiver impedance is negligible in the frequency range of interest. Factor of 4 in the first term of equation 2.3 appears if one carefully considers the contributions of forward and backwards moving travelling waves.

Finally, e_n^2 describes the total front-end noise contribution, which is conveniently described in RF engineering units with e_n taking value of a few nV/ $\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$. Note that calculation presented in the conceptual design report reduces to the same in the appropriate limits of short dipole.

For the cross-correlation, the calculation is essentially the same with a few minor modifications. The beam B is replaced with a cross-beam, which for a pair of antennas A and B is given by $B_{\times} = \vec{E}_A \cdot \vec{E}_B^*$. This is in general a complex quantity corresponding to the complex observed visibility in the cross-correlation. To derive the fraction of the cross-beam that is coupled to the ground, we need to know the value of $\int B_{\times} d\Omega$. This integral is zero for electrically decoupled antennas, which is not the case for the closely coupled LuSEE-Night pseudo-dipole. Instead, the level of coupling is calculated from pairs of simulations in which we excite either a single or both monopoles. Finally, the radiometer equation variance is distributed equally between the real and imaginary part of the cross-correlation.

We have implemented a signal simulation code. This code uses the Ultra Long wavelength Sky model with Absorption (ULSA) sky model [28] as a sky model. It combines the beam shapes as a function of frequency together with `astropy` and `lunarsky` based astronomy facilities to predict the antenna temperatures as a function of time. The integration of the sky signal and the beam has been performed in harmonic space for speed and numerical stability. The lunar ground is assumed to be at 0K. Given that the sky is considerably brighter than this, this is a very good approximation. The measured signals have been transformed into voltage power spectrum as described above. In Figure 2.3 we summarize the results of this exercise. See caption for detailed discussion of this plot. Our instantaneous signal to noise (i.e. for $\sqrt{Bt} = 1$) is forecasted to be around 40 with majority of signal coming from auto-correlation. This plot demonstrates that our design is capable of fulfilling the key performance parameter #3. Over a typical 1s integration we should see the galactic signal with very high signal-to-noise across the band.

2.3.3 Forecasts for monopole signal sensitivity

Forecasting the LuSEE-Night sensitivity to existence of any small monopole signal is difficult. To do it without simplifying assumptions would require advanced modelling that would entail all possible secondary effects including those that break the 4-fold symmetry of the experiment. It would also require advanced statistical modelling techniques that are currently under development. Nevertheless, an approximate analysis is useful not only in order to understand the basic scientific reach of the experiment, but also to better understand various trade-offs in experimental design. We also want an approach that is reasonably easy to understand and robust in its answers.

The Dark Ages signal is considerably more difficult to constrain than the cosmic dawn trough at 75 MHz. The signal itself is significantly weaker while the sky foregrounds are considerably brighter,

Figure 2.4: The foreground eigen-basis analysis for monopole auto-correlations. The variations in the sky signal are presented in the basis that diagonalizes the foreground variations around the mean. The blue line shows variance in the foregrounds in this basis. The orange line shows the same, after the 18 month noise covariance matrix is added. We see that the noise starts to dominate above 20th eigenvalue. Any monopole component is extractable from the data, if it is above the orange line in the presence of noise. Signals above the blue line might be reachable with deeper integration. Signals below the blue line are irretrievably lost to foregrounds in this model (but might be extractable with more sophisticated statistical modeling). We see that the Dark Ages signal with amplitude of 200K is measurable with high signal-to-noise. A monopole of uniform temperature, such as CMB is lost to foregrounds and even considerably brighter signal such as a 200K monopole (comparable to lunar ground loading) is essentially lost in the noise.

but most importantly it is considerably less sharp as a fraction of central peak position, making it more difficult to constrain in the presence of general foregrounds. Moreover, foregrounds at these lowest frequencies are not well described by power-laws due to free-free absorption [29].

We therefore pursue purely data-driven building of foreground models. We start by performing a principal component analysis of the signal for a particular type of antenna correlation product after we have subtracted the mean signal. Since the level of any monopole signal received does not vary with time (ignoring gain fluctuations for the time being), the existence of dark ages signal will not contaminate this signal. We then assume that the mean value of foreground signal is also well described by the same dominant linear components. For achromatic antennas this is likely an excellent assumption, since any piece of foreground will come into the beam view gradually (except at the south lunar celestial pole). In case of chromatic beams, the PCA components need to additionally absorb chromaticity effects and are less likely to work a-priori. Still, in practice, at least for ULSA sky and simulated beams, the filtering still seems to work very well. The dominant PCA components describe the possible smooth variations of the foregrounds as seen by the instrument. We can then express the variance of both foregrounds, the signal in this so-called foreground eigen-basis. The hope is that there will be components in this basis where the signal of interest

Figure 2.5: Sensitivity calculations to monopole signal represented by the rescaled Dark Ages signal. The forecast was done using the foreground eigen-basis analysis subjects to the caveats described in the text assuming 18 month integration on the lunar surface. These forecasts were performed for the detection significance of 50 sigma to take into account complexities of a real experiment. The y-axis is sky temperature in K, while the x-axis is frequency or the location in frequency of the rescaled Dark Ages signal. The black line represents the Novaco-Brown 1979 measurement, the dashed line is an estimate of the current limits at 20% of the monopole and the dotted line is 10^{-3} of the Novaco-Brown signal as our scientific goal. Solid colored lines correspond to the minimum detectable amplitude of the signal (at 50 sigma significance) as a function of signal width. Our sensitivity to narrow signals is significantly better as these are easier to distinguish from foreground variations. LuSEE-Night will improve by orders of magnitude over majority of parameter space, for narrow templates we are also performing significantly better than our science goals. Nevertheless, the actual Dark Ages trough marked with a blue star remains out of reach of this path-finder experiment.

and foregrounds separate cleanly. This is illustrated in the Figure 2.4 for auto-correlation channel with LuSEE-Night. Even with noise-less data and ULSA map, the full Dark Ages signal is out of reach, since the noise is dominated by the foreground uncertainty. However, signals that are brighter or narrower in frequency space are accessible by LuSEE-Night as we discuss below. We have also tested this method on noise-less ULSA map with small achromatic beams and there it is indeed possible to separate the Dark-Ages signal fairly cleanly after imposing a galaxy cut. This means that a subsequent experiment should be able to detect the dark ages signal provided a sufficient control over beam chromaticity has been achieved.

We note that this method is in principle quite robust, because the foreground separation does not depend at all on our knowledge of beam and its frequency dependence including any electronics effects. It is somewhat sensitive to gain fluctuations since these will map a uniform component into a variable one that will be picked up by the PCA analysis, so gain fluctuations needs to be kept at the minimum. The knowledge of the beam does enter *after* foreground separation when a template of the signal is calculated. We note that the available components in the PCA basis are quite non-uniform, therefore the information does not come from broad features in the peak, but instead from the fine feature details. For example, replacing dark ages signal with a Gaussian of the same position, width and amplitude has significant effects on sensitivity. Finally, improvements to this technique are almost certainly possible. For example, when the galactic center is below lunar horizon, the sky becomes certainly easier to model. The PCA is a rather crude-technique and results depend on the frequency weighting employed. Over the next few years we will make methodological improvements. At the same time, we recognize that the ULSA sky is certainly an oversimplification of the actual radio sky and that additional sources of emission such as planetary emission will make our data more difficult to model. Therefore, the present modelling attempts should be viewed as ball-park estimates of the achievable science.

To get a better understanding of the sensitivity of LuSEE-Night experiment we have created a library of templates. We have started with the Dark Ages trough calculated by the Accelerated Reionization Era Simulations (ARES) code [30]. We have smoothly interpolated the signal to zero at 50MHz (where the actual signal starts a down-turn towards the epoch of reionization trough). By transposing and stretching the signal in frequency and amplitude, we can create a signal of arbitrary minimum position, width and depth. The true Dark Ages template is recovered at mean of 16.4MHz, width of 14MHz and depth of -0.04K. We then proceed to forecast the detectability of our signal. Results are presented in Figure 2.5 together with science goals. We see that over the majority of the signal space our constraints are below 10^{-3} level of the foreground signal. For narrow peaks we are significantly better than 10^{-3} and reach sensitivity below 1K, which becomes interesting. Note that this figure has been calculated assuming a 50 sigma requirement on detection to give some buffer to our predictions. This means that in practice we might do considerably better, especially for narrow features.

This section verifies that our design can achieve the stated science objective #4 and might perform considerably better in some parts of parameter space.

3 SUBSYSTEMS DESCRIPTION

3.1 ANTENNAS

3.1.1 Overview

The purpose of the antenna assembly is to couple to an incident signal and provide voltage output for the amplifier and the spectrometer. Design goals are:

- Achieve strong enough coupling strength between 0.5 MHz to 50 MHz to observe galactic foregrounds and Dark Ages signal
- Have sensitivity to linear polarization to distinguish galactic foregrounds from Dark Ages signal
- Vary antenna orientation for systematic error check
- Smooth antenna impedance and beam as a function of frequency
- Total mass of the assembly to be less than 7.8 Kg
- Antenna can be stowed in a compact package during a flight
- Size of the assembly to fit on top of the LuSEE-Night outer box
- Antennas to not block the solar panels significantly
- High technology readiness level for on-time delivery

The antenna assembly design we decided on consists of four three meter monopole antennas that are mounted on a motorized turntable. The CAD image of the antenna assembly design is shown in Figure 3.1.

The monopole antennas are mounted 90 degrees from each other to probe polarization properties of an incident signal. The lengths of the monopole antennas are three meters. The antennas are mounted at 4 degrees above the horizon to account for sag due to the moon's gravity. The deployed antennas will rest horizontally to maximize their coupling strength.

We mount four antennas as close to each other as possible while keeping enough space for the hole in middle of the turntable for the communication antenna and the cable feed through. The diameter of the turntable is 500 mm. The 500 mm diameter turntable fits nicely on top of the LuSEE-Night module. The turntable will rotate ± 95 degrees to sweep over various linear polarization directions. The turntable will be mounted on the outside surface of the LuSEE-Night instrument console.

We will use a DC servo motor for the turntable actuation. Positions of the rotation stage will be monitored by an encoder. Encoder signal will be sent back to the low EMI power supply slice that is housed inside of the LuSEE-Night module. We will also monitor temperature of the motor to ensure that the motor is operated only when it is safe to do so.

3.1.2 Antenna

Antenna selection Several requirements and constraints outlined above were considered to select an antenna. We looked into monopole antenna, loop antenna, log-periodic antenna, discone antenna and Vivaldi antenna.

Broadband antennas such as log-periodic antenna, discone antenna and Vivaldi antenna can achieve smooth impedance and beam performance with high coupling factor over wide range of frequency band. In addition, end fire antennas like log-periodic antenna and Vivaldi antenna have

the desirable property that the beam can be pointed in one direction. But in order to take advantage of a broadband antenna's performance, antennas need to be appropriately sized. Such an antenna would be over 10 meters to cover our frequency of interest. We looked into approaches people have taken to make such antenna portable. ALARIS antennas designed a portable log-periodic antenna for 80 MHz to 3000 MHz range. However, their single polarization version of the antenna already weighed 18 Kg. We also looked into approaches in the cube-sat community. One company printed a conductive log-periodic antenna pattern on a flexible membrane that could be folded into compact format. MMA DESIGN designed a printed antenna for 350 MHz to 2000 MHz range that fit within 1U (10 cm x 10 cm x 10 cm) of volume. Although these antenna had desirable characteristics, broadband antennas did not meet our weight and size constraints.

We also studied a loop antenna. It has similar beam characteristics as a dipole antenna, but it has an interesting feature that its real impedance can be boosted by increasing number of turns. However, even with increased number of turns (suppose N 10), radiation efficiency remains low for electrically small loop antenna even with a good conductor like copper. Also, there was no available design that is portable and has high technology readiness level.

After studying these alternative antenna options, we decided to deploy four monopole antennas. We will deploy electrically small antennas such that the antennas have smooth impedance and beam response as a function of frequency. Unfortunately, electrically small monopole antennas have small real impedance (thus small open circuit voltage) and large reactance. We later show that the monopole antenna configuration we have chosen achieves required performance.

Design of the monopole antenna is based on the "stacer" antenna that was deployed in the STEREO/WAVES experiment [31]. Stacer antennas have been deployed in multiple astrophysics satellite missions used either as an antenna or a boom to support an instrument. A stacer is a rolled beryllium copper sheet with a constant helical pitch that acts as a flat spring. It can be compressed in a stowed position in a small package until it is deployed. Deployment is triggered by actuating a shaped memory alloy pin.

Figure 3.1: (Left) CAD image of the antenna unit. The stacer antenna and the preamp box is mounted on the θ rotation stage. Four θ stages are mounted on the black ϕ rotation platform. Each stage is actuated by DC servo motors. (Right) Photograph of the stacer antenna that was deployed in the STEREO/WAVES experiment [31]

Simulation comparison We compared three electromagnetic simulator packages, HFSS, CST and FEKO, to understand how the antenna performs and to make sure that simulators are used correctly. Computation algorithms used by these simulators are different. HFSS and CST use the finite element method whereas FEKO uses a method of moments. We compared the results to analytical results

from a text book whenever they are available to cross-check our result [32]. We modeled the antenna, the surface of the instrumentation enclosure and the lander as a perfectly conducting polygon as shown in Figure 3.2. We modeled the lunar regolith as an eight layer dielectric slab with gradually increasing dielectric constants and absorption factors following recent re-analysis of the Apollo-17 mission data [33]. Both HFSS and FEKO have an ability to simulate infinitely thick dielectric layers and dielectric layers with certain thickness, dielectric constant and losses. We increased a complexities of the model gradually all the way to the four monopole antennas on the LuSEE-Night module with a lander on a complex multi-layer dielectric soil that mimics the lunar environment. Simulation results agreed between different simulators to an accuracy we need to make design choices as shown in Figure 3.2 and Figure 3.3. Further study is being conducted to understand small discrepancies between simulations.

Figure 3.2: (Left) Example of antenna beam profile from HFSS EM simulator. Colors indicate amplitude of the gain of the antenna beam. Simulated structure can be seen inside of the beam. (Right) Comparison of real and imaginary components of antenna impedance between HFSS and FEKO for the pseudo-dipole mode of the monopole antennas of LuSEE-Night on lunar soil. There is good agreement between the results of the two simulators with a slight deviation on $Re(Z)$ component below 10 MHz.

Figure 3.3: Example of antenna beam comparisons between HFSS and FEKO. Three radiation patterns are shown at ϕ slices of 0, 45, and 90 degrees. The beams are from the pseudo-dipole mode of the monopole antennas of LuSEE-Night on lunar soil.

Antenna configuration The antenna module will consist of four monopole stacer antennas that are mounted on the turntable. All four antennas will be 3 meters long. All antennas will have the same diameter (0.35 inch on average) with the same metal thickness (0.005"), and they will be made out of beryllium copper. Antenna housing will be made out of magnesium to save weight. Material choices follow previously flown stacer antenna units [31]. Pin puller mechanism will be used to lock/deploy the antenna. We will use TiNi pin puller (size P5) from Ensign-Bickford Aerospace and Defense. This pin puller was also used in previous flight missions. Each antenna package weighs 750 gram to meet our goal of keeping weight of the antenna module below 7.8 Kg. The antennas will deploy 4 degrees above the horizon, such that the antennas rest horizontal after their expected sag. We will pack the antenna as close as possible on the turntable to keep the turntable as small as possible to save weight and torque required to turn the turntable. We explain how we came to the design below.

Figure 3.4: (Left) Equivalent circuit model of antenna circuit. R_{ant} and X_{ant} are real and imaginary antenna impedance. 35 pF capacitance arises from stray capacitance between stacer antenna and antenna housing body and cables. $R = 1\text{ M}\Omega$ was selected to maximize output voltage while minimizing Johnson noise. (Right) Coordinate system used to calculate effective temperature seen by the antenna.

We first developed a formalism to calculate open circuit voltage at antenna terminal when antenna is immersed in a radiation with effective temperature T_{eff} . We assumed equivalent circuit in Figure 3.4 to calculate the voltage spectrum delivered to the preamp's input (V_{out}) [32]. R_{ant} and X_{ant} are real and imaginary components of antenna impedance, respectively. Open circuit voltage at antenna terminal can be calculated as [34]:

$$V_{oc} = \sqrt{4k_B T_{eff} R_{ant} \Delta f} \quad (3.1)$$

Where k_B is a Boltzmann constant, T_{eff} is an effective temperature of the radiation that the antenna is immersed in, R_{ant} is the real component of antenna impedance, and Δf is the bandwidth.

Figure 3.5: (Left) Fraction of the radiated beam that goes to the ground as determined by EM simulations. (Middle) Temperature on the lunar surface over the course of a lunar day. Latitudes have a dramatic effect on the daytime temperature. (Right) Effective brightness temperature of the antenna given a synchrotron-dominated sky.

Because LuSEE-Night will observe from the surface of the moon, the antenna sees both lunar soil and sky. Effective temperature that antenna sees can be calculated by integrating over gain of the antenna as

$$T_{\text{eff}} = T_{\text{sky}} \frac{\int_0^\pi \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} G(\theta, \phi) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi}{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi G(\theta, \phi) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi} + T_{\text{ground}} \frac{\int_0^\pi \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} G(\theta, \phi) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi}{\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi G(\theta, \phi) \sin(\theta) d\theta d\phi} \quad (3.2)$$

We simplify the equation by defining fraction of radiated beam that goes to sky and ground as f_{sky} and f_{ground} respectively. Using these term, we can simplify above equation as

$$T_{\text{eff}} = T_{\text{sky}} f_{\text{sky}} + T_{\text{ground}} f_{\text{ground}} \quad (3.3)$$

Where by definition, $f_{\text{sky}} = 1 - f_{\text{ground}}$. f_{ground} , lunar temperature, and sky temperature as a function of lunar hour are given in Figure 3.5. f_{ground} did not change much as a function of antenna length. We assumed lunar soil temperature of 140 Kelvin during lunar night observation [35]. We used Cane's sky model and assumed uniform sky temperature in the initial calculation for simplicity [27]. We use a complex sky model that includes angular dependence in the full analysis of the instrument performance.

The shunt capacitance in the circuit arises from stray capacitance between the stacer antennas and surrounding structures such as antenna housings. We assumed 35 pF for this capacitance taken from past experiences from STEREO/WAVES experiment and Parker Solar Probe that also deployed similar stacer antennas [31].

Figure 3.6 shows how antenna impedance and beams change as we change antenna length from 1 meter to 6 meters. Short antenna (1 meter) has smooth impedance and beam property as a function of frequency, but it has weak coupling due to small radiation resistance. Radiation resistance increases as antenna becomes longer, but complexities of impedance and beam increases.

Figure 3.6: (Left) Effects on impedance as the antenna length is varied. Longer antennas have larger real impedances but introduce resonances. Resonance frequencies move towards lower frequencies as the antennas become longer. All antennas are deployed at 75 degrees from zenith. (Right) Radiation pattern ($\phi = 0^\circ$, angle in the xy-plane) of the antenna beam at 20 MHz as the antenna length is varied. Shorter antennas have lower gain, but the shape remains unchanged.

Next we studied how changing angles between opposing pairs of antennas will affect antenna performance. Changing this "V" angle did not change antenna impedance significantly as shown in Figure 3.7. This will not provide a useful change in output voltage as a function of frequency. Also, the real part of the impedance decreased as the V-angle between antennas became smaller (more acute) as expected. We also observed that beam shape did not change strongly, especially when antenna is electrically small compared to the frequency of interest. We therefore decided to not move antennas in θ (V-angle) to reduce number of moving parts and therefore improve reliability. We also decided to deploy antenna in horizontal orientation to maximize radiation resistance to maximize voltage output.

Figure 3.7: (Left) Effects on impedance as the antenna angle (θ) is varied. Decreasing θ (from zenith) has little effect on the frequencies of the resonances, however, it does lower the real impedance, especially at extremely narrow angles. All antennas are 3 meters in length. (Right) Radiation pattern ($\phi = 0^\circ$) of the antenna beam at 20 MHz as the antenna angle is varied. Narrower antenna angles decreases the gain of the beam, but the shape remains unchanged.

We then studied effect of output resistor on the voltage spectrum that will be delivered to preamp from antenna. We varied output resistor's value by orders of magnitude and studied how output voltage changed as a function of voltage as shown in Figure 3.8. We observed that any resistance above 10 k Ω will not diminish output voltage. We then studied how Johnson noise from the resistor will affect voltage noise at the output as a function of resistances. As shown in Figure 3.8, effect of Johnson noise becomes negligible above 1 M Ω . Since performance would not change above 1 M Ω , we used 1 M Ω as baseline resistor value, but any resistance higher would work as well. For example, STEREO/WAVES experiment used a 150 M Ω for this resistor [31].

Figure 3.8: (Left) Voltage power at the receiver terminal with varying internal receiver resistance. Beyond 10 k Ω the voltage power plateaus. (Right) Johnson noise generated voltage power at receiver terminal with varying internal receiver resistance. Beyond 100 Ω the generated Johnson noise monotonically decreases.

We calculated output voltage using antenna impedance and beam from simulations, effective temperature, and equivalent circuit model. The expected output voltage spectrum as the antenna observes the sky from the surface of the moon is plotted in Figure 3.9. We added two white noise

lines to show if we have instantaneous sensitivity to see galactic signal above instrumental noise. We then calculated signal to noise ratio of detecting Dark Ages dip after integrating for 10 days. The goal of this exercise is to understand how antenna length affect observation of dark ages signal with a simple model for relative comparison. Full analysis was then performed on selected antenna configurations. With this simple analysis, we were able to conclude that antenna lengths shorter than two meters would not have a signal to noise high enough to detect the Dark Ages signal. We have run detailed study for 2, 2.5 and 3 meter antenna length. After the full analysis that is outlined in the previous section, we baselined to deploy four 3 meter antennas.

Figure 3.9: (Left) Voltage power at receiver terminals given the effective brightness temperature of the antennas and a synchrotron-dominant sky. Noise values are shown for reference. (Right) Signal to noise ratio. The instantaneous SNR is defined as the ratio of RMS voltage power at the receiver terminal with the total receiver noise. The receiver noise is a superposition of the intrinsic JFET noise and the Johnson noise of the antennas transferred to the receiver, added in quadrature. SNR are given for two different typical intrinsic JFET receiver noise values. The instantaneous SNR is then integrated over the length of 1 lunar night (choosing a conservative 10 Earth days) with a 1 MHz bandwidth. We approximate the SNR against the Dark Ages signal by factoring in the ratio of the effective temperature of the Dark Ages to the synchrotron sky.

Antenna Placement above Lunar Surface The lander vendor and design are not known at this stage of the project. Therefore we studied the sensitivity of the antenna performance to various shapes of the lander and effect of distance between the antenna and surface of the moon.

Examples shown in Figure 3.10 and Figure 3.11 shows how varying distance between the antenna and surface of the moon changes antenna performance. We saw no strong effect on antenna impedance. f_{ground} reduced as the distance between the antenna and surface of the moon increased. This is expected as the antenna beam gets disturbed less by the lunar soil as the distance increases. Finally, antenna beam became more complex as the distance increases. This is expected behavior as number of lobes in the beam is [32],

$$N_{lobes} \sim 2 \frac{h}{\lambda} \quad (3.4)$$

Where h is the distance between antenna and reflective element (in our case surface of the moon) and λ is the wavelength.

There is a trade off between sensitivity and the beam complexity to decide on the distance between the antenna module to surface of the moon. We weighted simplicity in beam structure

more heavily to select a range of 2.5 meters to 3.5 meters as a baseline. At this height, we can achieve enough sensitivity to galactic emission and Dark Ages signal while keeping beam complexity minimal.

Figure 3.10: (Left) Effects on impedance as the height to the base of the antennas is varied. Changing the antenna height only has an appreciable effect on the real impedance below 10 MHz. The shift in antenna resonances seen in the imaginary impedance are predominantly a result of the simulation resolution of 1 MHz. (Right) Fraction of the radiated beam that goes to the ground as the height is varied. Below ~ 30 MHz, increasing the height causes f_{ground} to drop more rapidly resulting in a shift to lower frequencies of the minimum. Past ~ 30 MHz, f_{ground} lowers as height increases.

Figure 3.11: Radiation patterns ($\phi = 0^\circ$) at 10, 30, and 50 MHz as a function of antenna height. At low frequencies antenna gain is primarily effected, at mid frequencies the relative strength of the zenith facing lobe vs sidelobes are effected, and at high frequencies the number of lobes is additionally a large factor. The beams are from the pseudo-dipole mode of the monopole antennas of LuSEE-Night on lunar soil.

Future simulation work We have completed various antenna simulations to determine our baseline design. There were many unknowns, but the model we used in the simulation is accurate enough to make decisions for the baseline design. We will continue to refine simulations as we will use results from antenna simulations for tolerance analysis and scientific data analysis. We listed parameters that we would like to improve in future simulation work.

Finite conductivity, dielectric property - So far we assumed the antenna, the LuSEE-Night module and the lander to be a perfect electric conductor. As we start to decide on actual materials we are going to use, we would like to update the simulation with appropriate material properties to capture effects of finite conductivity. For example, we will assign antenna's material property as beryllium copper to see how radiation efficiency get affected due to its finite conductivity.

Lander and auxiliary parts information Due to how the CLPS program is organized, we do not know information about the lander at this moment. We learned through the simulations that some antenna properties (especially f_{ground}) change as a function of shape of the lander. Also, we have not included conductive structures such as communication antenna in the model. Once we have information about these items, we will refine our simulations.

Lunar regolith dielectric sweep Antenna performance is affected by dielectric properties of the lunar regolith. We are modeling the lunar regolith as eight layer dielectric slabs with gradually increasing dielectric constant and absorption following recent re-analysis of the Apollo-17 mission data [33]. However, this data came from front side of the moon, there is no reliable data of dielectric property of lunar regolith from far side of the moon. We plan to vary dielectric constant, loss and their profile as a function of depth to calculate how uncertainty in lunar regolith property affect our data analysis.

Landing site We are planning to land on a site that is flat, where hills are low and far from the landing site, and does not have anomalies such as high magnetic field. Example of a target landing site is shown in Figure 3.12. Despite a flat landing site, we could expect to land at some angle. We are expecting to land within ± 10 degrees. We will simulate effect of such tilt. We could also calculate effect of hills in the far field (far field starts around a few meters past the lander) using geometrical optics techniques.

Figure 3.12: (Left) Horizon angle created by local topography as a function of azimuthal angle as seen from a potential LuSEE landing site. 0 degrees azimuth corresponds to due north with the azimuthal angle increasing clockwise (to the east). This horizon profile was generated by the SHAPES code presented in Bassett et al. 2021 using a digital elevation model derived from both the Lunar Orbiter Laser Altimeter and SELENE terrain camera instruments (Barker et al. 2016). (Right) Map showing the local topography surrounding the potential landing site. The black curve traces the topographical features that define the horizon profile at each azimuthal angle. Elevation is given relative to a lunar radius of 1,737,400 m.

3.1.3 Motorized Stage

Motorized stage configuration The four antenna modules will be mounted equidistant on a turntable of diameter ~ 500 mm and thickness ~ 10 mm. Three common engineering materials are being considered for the turntable platter: aluminum, titanium, or carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP).

A machined aluminum plate would be the least expensive to fabricate. Detractions are the higher CTE (~ 12 - 25 ppm/K over the 100-400 K temperature range) and reduced stress allowables at sustained high temperature (7075-T651 aluminum, for example, may have yield strength reduction from ~ 500 MPa at room temperature to ~ 180 MPa when sustained at 150°C (423 K). The high thermal conductivity of aluminum allows faster heat transfer toward the spacecraft. All these detractions can likely be mitigated with use of appropriate design allowables and thermal breaks.

Grade 5 titanium would be a robust solution. Material cost would be comparable to CFRP, though fabrication complexity would be simpler. CTE is relatively low and stable (~ 5 - 9 ppm/K over range 100-400 K), strength is high, and the very low thermal conductivity (~ 5 - 8 W/m/K) would provide some natural insulation of the rest of the spacecraft from the exposed turntable's temperature. For cost and ease of manufacturing we would probably not machine the plate out of thick titanium, but rather screw together a thinner face sheet with stiffening ribs.

CFRP would have a higher stiffness per unit mass than the metals, as well as some natural structural damping. We would likely use an intermediate modulus fiber in a quasi-isotropic, balanced, symmetric layup. Matrix would be 350°F (450 K) cured resin such as Toray RS-3C, commonly used in spacecraft. The design would need to be sufficiently low-strain such that the total temperature change from processing (450 K) down to lunar night (100 K) does not exceed fiber strain limits. A honeycomb sandwich construction would be most mass-efficient, with titanium or aluminum inserts at bolted connections. Thermal expansion effects would be low, several parts per million (ppm) per degree K. Low out-of-plane thermal conductivity would be of some benefit in reducing the heat transfer rate from the turntable to the rest of the spacecraft below it. The main detraction of CFRP are the higher design and fabrication costs.

We selected to use DC servo motor over a stepper motor for the weight and complexity of the motor controller. We will use a gearmotor A-1430 from Globe motor that was previously flown in the Themis mission. When ordering the motor, we will pay specific attention to a bearing seal, a type of lubricant that can withstand vacuum environment, and types of plating. It will be mated with Kayden KA025AR0 bearing for rotation. Rotation of the turntable will be monitored by an encoder that will be mounted on a motor head. We will also attach a thermometer on the motor to make sure that the motor is actuated only when temperature of the motor is in safe range for lubricant. Lunar dust is a concern for the motor and the bearing. We make a well sealed design to protect the motor and the bearing.

Range of motion of the turn table is ± 95 degrees. We are targeting angle accuracy of less than 1 deg. We are currently working through calculation to make sure that the motor has enough torque (2oz. in.) to turn the turntable even if we land tilted by 10 degrees. The turntable will be locked with a FC2 TiNi frangibolt from Ensign-Bickford Aerospace and Defense that was also flown in previous space mission.

The motor (A-1430-14) weighs 200g, the bearing (KA025AR0) weighs 55 gram, and the frangibolt weighs 25 gram. A turntable of diameter ~ 0.5 m and thickness ~ 10 mm machined out of solid disk of aluminum would weigh 5.3 Kg. Combined with expected total weight of 3 Kgs from the antennas and conservative estimate of 500 gram for the cables, we will need to reduce weight of

the turntable disk. We will cut away weight reduction holes in the aluminum plate, so that we meet the 8 Kg weight target.

Power for the motor, encoder readout signal and thermometer readout will be fed into PFPS unit. They will be connected via flexible cable with enough length to accommodate the ± 95 degrees rotations. The frangibolt will be triggered with power from PDU unit.

Mode of Operation We will move the turntable during the lunar day when more electrical power is available. Also, we will move the turntable when we are in contact with communication antenna.

After the lander lands, PDU will supply power to trigger the frangibolt. We will check successful actuation by looking at the encoder signal. The pin-pullers on the stacer antennas will also be triggered by the PDU. We will monitor signals on pre-amp to see if the antenna deployed as expected. We also requested the lander to provide photograph of the antenna unit after the deployment.

During the regular observation we will move the turntable during the lunar day when more electrical power is available. We will first check thermometer reading to make sure that the motor is in safe temperature range. Then power for the motor is delivered from PFPS. It will supply $\pm 12V$ to motor while reading out encoder. Power to the motor, the encoder, and the thermometer will be turned off for the night observation.

3.1.4 Integration and Testing

The antenna module can be integrated and tested independently prior to being integrated with other modules.

The turntable can be tested by itself to check for range of the motion, torque that it can generate, and power draw using lab bench power supply. We will also test the motor and the bearing's ability to survive temperature swing in a vacuum environment by thermal cycling them in a dewar.

The stacer antenna's deployment mechanism can also be tested by itself. After assembling the antenna, we will check for the operation of the memory alloy pin, deployment speed and sag due to earth gravity. The antenna's EM performance such as antenna impedance can also be checked independently by connecting the antenna to a 4-port Vector Network Analyzer. It will be challenging to make accurate measurements since the antenna will interact with its surroundings in the laboratory setting. We will utilize various techniques such as moving to open field, surrounding antenna with absorbers, and time gated measurements to compare measurements against simulations. Stray capacitance is an important parameter to calculate the expected performance. We will follow methods used by STEREO/Waves and Parker Solar Probe missions to measure stray capacitance of the module [31].

3.2 SPECTROMETER

3.2.1 Description

The LuSEE-Night spectrometer will be an enhanced version of the RF Spectrometer (RFS) flown as part of the FIELDS instrument suite on the Parker Solar Probe ([3], [36]), see Figure 3.13. The new (original) spectrometer acquires spectra over the 0.5 - 50 (0.1 - 20) MHz band from pairs of monopole antennas using 4 (2) digitizers sampling at 120 (38.4) Msps and a radiation-tolerant FPGA in 65nm (150nm) CMOS technology, otherwise retaining much of the structure and processing

Figure 4. DCB/RFS FM board. The RFS analog electronics are isolated from the main board in the area in the upper right corner of the DCB/RFS. The DCB FPGA is not shown in this image; when installed, the FPGA resides in the space on the lower left side of the board.

Spectrometer parameter	Experiment	
	Parker RFS (HF channel)	LuSEE-Night
Frequency range	0.01 – 19.2 MHz	0.5 – 50.0 MHz
Digitizer channels	2	4
Sampling clock	39 MSPS	100 MSPS
Duty factor	~1%	~100%
FPGA	RTAX4000	RTG4
Correlation products	2	6
Transient capture	No	Yes

Figure 3.13: Above: The Parker Solar Probe Radiofrequency spectrometer (from [36]), block diagram and PC board layout. Below: modifications for LuSEE-Night.

elements of the earlier design. An overall block diagram of the LuSEE-Night Spectrometer is shown in Figure 3.14.

3.2.2 Analog section

The analog section of the spectrometer is responsible for conditioning the signals from the monopole antennas and forming the signal combinations for digitization. The design is adopted from the Parker Solar Probe Radiofrequency Spectrometer [36] with modifications to fulfill the requirements of LuSEE-Night. Single-ended signals from the four antenna-mounted preamps are routed via coax cable to connectors on the frame of the RF Spectrometer slice in the MEC. As shown in Figure 3.14 each of the four signal chains consists of a preamplifier, difference amplifier, gain stages, and an anti-aliasing filter. A balun converts the outgoing single-ended signal to differential input to the ADC.

The analog signal chain has been designed to meet the following performance goals:

- Input noise voltage spectral density: $e_n : 2\text{--}5\text{nV}/\sqrt{\text{Hz}}$
- Capacitance at preamp input: $\leq 5\text{ pF}$, not including strays
- 3dB bandwidth: 0.5 - 50 MHz
- Voltage gain: selectable, 57dB (high gain), 23 dB (low gain)

As shown in Section 3.1, the sky signal from the antenna is expected to be in the range of 1 - 10

Figure 3.14: Spectrometer block diagram showing interfaces to the antenna preamps and C&DH Board.

nV/\sqrt{Hz} . The noise contributed by the analog chain will be dominated by the preamp, and will have a similar magnitude even after selecting the lowest-noise components meeting the bandwidth and capacitance requirements (lower noise is attainable at the cost of increased input capacitance, which worsens the antenna mismatch factor; see Section 2.3). The gain specification (high-gain mode) is chosen to make the ADC quantization noise contribution negligible, while capturing the galactic foreground signal and any EMI noise peaks without saturating; low gain mode will be used when more energetic RF emissions are present. The arrangement of the gains through the chain is indicated in Figure 3.15

The full analog signal chain design has been completed at the level of component selection, circuit schematics, and AC and noise simulations. All components are radiation tolerant to levels beyond the expected mission dose. Simulation results are shown in Figure 3.16. The analog section power supply is $\pm 5V$ and simulated power dissipation for the full 4-channel section is about 1.6W.

Figure 3.15: One channel of the analog signal chain. Stage gains shown in green.

Figure 3.16: SPICE simulations of the analog chain. Left: gains (high gain mode). Right: equivalent input noise density.

3.2.3 Digital section

The digital section of the spectrometer includes the multiplexer tree and gain control, digitizers, spectrum processor, snapshot processor, calibration processor, clock management, and interface to the Control/Data Handling board.

Depending on the observation mode chosen, the multiplexer tree will be set up to pass the difference of antenna pairs (or antenna-ground) to each digitizer. The initial gain range will be automatically set to accommodate the expected signal strength and then adjusted by monitoring the data stream. The frequency plan is to put the LuSEE-Night band within the first Nyquist zone, implying a sampling rate $f_s \geq 100\text{MSPS}$. To adequately cover the expected dynamic range the effective number of bits (ENOB) must be ≥ 11 .

Within the spectrum processor, the elements are:

1. Overrange sensing and gain adjust: when the ADC output is pinned at full scale an algorithm will select the appropriate action: flag or discard the data, reduce analog gain, etc.
2. Decimation filter: if possible, we will oversample the data and use an FIR filter to reduce the complexity of the analog anti-aliasing filter. Depends on the availability of a sufficiently fast ADC.
3. Channelizer and RFI notch filter: a frame of time-sampled data of appropriate length is apodized and processed into a number (256 - 2048) of spectral channels by polyphase filterbank. Each bin's spectral leakage can be tailored by appropriate filter coefficients, and optional notch filter(s) can be incorporated at the frequencies where the RFI 'picket-fence' peaks are expected.
4. Corner turn: data is re-ordered as a matrix transpose to send same-frequency samples from channel pairs to the correlator.
5. Correlator: all auto- and cross-correlations of the four data streams will be calculated (sample-by-sample complex multiplication).
6. Accumulator: the correlation products will be averaged for a programmable integration time, likely in the range of 10s of seconds.
7. Data formatter: at the conclusion of each integration interval the data will be formatted and transferred to the C&DH for storage in NV memory.

The snapshot processor will bypass the channelizer and store a frame of raw samples to memory. This mode will be used for detection of transient phenomena and for diagnostics.

The calibration processor will be implemented when the parameters of the external calibrator are more fully defined (Section 3.6.1). The coded sequence in the calibrator will be preloaded into Spectrometer memory and a correlation engine will lock onto the received signal, a technique similar to that used in GPS receivers.

As discussed in Section 2, switching circuitry in the LuSEE-Night instrument will follow EMI requirements which mandate that all switching waveforms be slaved to a master clock distributed from C&DH. Within the Spectrometer special care needs to be taken to manage the multiple clock waveforms needed for operating ADCs, FPGA, and any switched voltage regulators, and to avoid interrupting return current paths. For further EMI reduction differential signaling, thick ground and power planes, faraday cages around sensitive analog nodes, and EMI gasketing around connectors and apertures may be used.

Key component choices have been finalized: For digitization, we will use two dual 14-bit, 125

Msamples/sec COTS parts (ADS4245-EP); signal processing functions will be handled via firmware in a radiation-hard, reprogrammable FPGA (Microsemi RTG4); 4Gb of rad-hard DDR memory (2X 3D-Plus 3d2d2G16ub2684) are provided for temporary data storage. A rad-hard current limiter (3D-Plus 3DPM0168) will be used to protect any COTS components from single-event latchup. Secondary power will be delivered from the PFPS and rad-hard regulators will develop the additional voltages required (see the next section). A preliminary board layout showing component placement (analog chains as well as digital section) is shown in Figure 3.17. The superimposed photograph of the 6" x 9" Parker Solar Probe board indicates that LuSEE-Night's spectrometer can occupy the same form factor. Preliminary power estimate for the complete Spectrometer board is 8.4W.

5

Figure 3.17: Preliminary component placement superimposed on photograph of the Parker Solar Probe RFS/DCB board.

3.2.4 FPGA Details

Figure 3.18 shows the main functional blocks of the Spectrometer FPGA. Interfaces to the C&DH/DPU (green) and to the analog section of the Spectrometer (blue) are also shown. The primary system clock is received from the C&DH/DPU and used to generate all timing on the board. The main data and control interface to the C&DH/DPU will use the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems (CCSDS) protocol; a backup channel which treats the FPGA as an I2C slave device is also included

for redundancy. The interface to the analog section includes the 125 MHz ADC sampling clocks, the ADC data, multiplexer tree and gain range configuration, and control of an analog multiplexer for monitoring temperatures, voltages, and supply current.

Figure 3.18: FPGA block diagram.

As illustrated in Figure 3.17, the Spectrometer board will include a mezzanine holding the FPGA. Figure 3.19 shows the I/O assignment and signalling levels to the mezzanine.

RTG 4 IO BANK Utilization & Approximate Pin count

Figure 3.19: FPGA mezzanine card I/O and preliminary pin count.

3.2.5 Board Power

Eight separate supply voltages are required to power the digital and analog sections of the Spectrometer. Rad-hard voltage regulators and a power sequencer will be used to derive the load voltages from a set of voltages supplied by the PFPS as shown in Figure 3.20: +3.6V (5A max), +2.8V/1.3A, and $\pm 5.5V/100mA$. All regulators except the ISL700002SEH (which handles the highest load current) are low-dropout linears; the DC/DC switching regulator will be slaved to the master clock to avoid EMI generation.

Upon the instrument reaching a power-positive state, the PFPS will supply power to the inputs of all regulators on the board with their ENABLE inputs pulled low. When ready the C&DH/DPU will raise the "PWR_EN" signal to the ISL70321SEH sequencer to initiate the FPGA power sequence. After FPGA initialization completes, the enable inputs for the analog regulators are pulled high. The analog regulators can be disabled by setting registers on the FPGA.

Figure 3.20: Powering arrangement for the Spectrometer board. Secondary power lines from the PFPS are sequenced and regulated to drive the loads on the digital and analog sections of the board.

3.2.6 Monitoring and Telemetry

The spectrometer gain will unavoidably be sensitive to temperature and power supply fluctuations; therefore it is necessary to monitor and compensate for these effects. The spectrometer and preamp boards will include thermistors and sense resistors at critical points to monitor temperatures, voltages, and power supply currents. The analog signals from these sensors will be periodically multiplexed and sent to housekeeping ADCs located on the DPU where they will be sampled, and merged into the instrument data stream.

3.2.7 Interfaces and Operating Modes

The spectrometer will have interfaces to the Antenna, Power Delivery, and C&DH subsystems. The mechanical and electronic details will be formally specified in Interface Control Documents.

Control commands for operation of the spectrometer will come from flight software on the C&DH/DPU using industry standard protocols. The DPU will be preprogrammed with standard operating sequences (power-on, sleep/wake, initialize, self-test, acquire [spectra/snapshot/calibration/housekeeping], dump acquired data, etc.) and configuration parameters (gain range setting, multiplexer setting, ADC sample rate, digital filter coefficients, PFB taps/resolution/notch, etc.). During Operation, settings can be modified from the mission operating center by uplink via the relay satellite. Spectrometer data, after averaging, is relatively low volume and can be transferred using moderate-rate interchange formats between the Spectrometer and the DPU.

3.3 MECHANICAL & THERMAL DESIGN

3.3.1 Inner Equipment Assembly Mechanical Structure

Figure 3.21 shows the baseline design for the instrument. The outer box (OB) will form the overall support structure for the antenna rotator, solar panels, radiator, and Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA). The IEA, shown in Figure 3.21 will consist of a battery, the Main Electronics Crate (MEC), communications module (RFCOM), and brackets to mount the thermal switches. The IEA will be surrounded by multi-layer insulation (MLI) (not shown).

The electronics and battery will generate heat, which needs to be maintained within an acceptable temperature range. Heat from the electronics and battery will be transferred to two thermal switches which will connect to an external radiator through two miniaturized loop heat pipes (mini-LHPs). When a thermal switch reaches a set temperature, it will close, allowing heat to flow to the radiator and be rejected to space. Likewise, if the temperature drops below a certain point, the thermal switch will open, retaining heat within the IEA. This method will allow the temperature of the IEA to be maintained within a set range.

Figure 3.21: Concept design for the LuSEE-Night instrument. On top are the four stacers. The Battery and MEC are mounted on a base plate supported by the outer crate. On the right is the parabolic radiator panel.

3.3.2 JPL Technical Interchange Meeting (TIM)

Staff from BNL and SSL met at NASA JPL to discuss thermal management technologies that may be of interest for LuSEE-Night. David Bugby and Jose Rivera shared information from their group's research for the Planetary and Lunar Environment Thermal Toolbox Elements (PALETTE) project. We would like to express our gratitude to the group at NASA for sharing this information, which has been extremely useful. We learned specifics on the inner and outer box design, thermal switch, radiator, and method of transferring heat to the radiator. Only general details will be discussed in this document.

The mechanical structure of PALETTE used a box-in-a-box design, in which an inner box was suspended by tension cables inside of an outer box. Multi-layer insulation surrounded the inner box to reduce heat transfer. This design resulted in low thermal conductivity, but at this time the LuSEE-Night team has decided to use a more traditional mounting strategy, discussed in another section.

We plan to use the same design for the thermal switches, radiator, and method of transferring heat to the radiator, which was developed as part of PALETTE. These components are the responsibility of

SSL. BNL will be responsible for everything on the IEA up to interfacing with the thermal switches. Due to the higher heat load on LuSEE-Night, we plan to use two thermal switches for the baseline design, though one larger thermal switch may eventually prove better from a thermal or weight standpoint.

3.3.3 Design Strategy

The mechanical engineering groups at BNL and SSL discussed baseline design strategies - either using the tension cable design from PALLETE or a more traditional mounting structure, with the IEA connected more directly to the outer box.

Comparing the two design strategies, the tension cable design has the benefit of low thermal conductivity, but it has greater mechanical complexity. A more traditional mounting structure will have greater thermal conductivity but lower complexity, require less mechanical analysis, and allow for easier assembly.

Compared to PALETTE, more heat is generated by the electronics and battery on LuSEE-Night. Preliminary analysis indicates that if we choose a suspended cable design, and therefore the least amount of thermal conductivity, the thermal switch would need to operate throughout the night to remove heat. Therefore, extreme thermal isolation is not required, meaning greater heat leaks are permissible, and a more traditional mounting strategy can be employed.

The following thermal analysis summary was written by SSL:

A thermal case study was conducted to find the sensitivity of the overall design to various thermal isolation methods. Once a basic size of the radiator was determined at 0.70 m^2 , the following cases were analyzed:

Case 1) Internal Equipment Assembly (IEA) isolated from the Outer Box with a box-in-a-box tension cable design and 10 layers of single layer insulation (SLI).

Case 2) IEA isolated from the Outer Box with a box-in-a-box tension cable design and traditional Multi-Layer Insulation (MLI) blankets.

Case 3) IEA isolated from the Outer Box with a traditional structural thermal isolator and 10 layers of SLI.

Case 4) IEA isolated from the Outer Box with a traditional structural thermal isolator and MLI blankets.

External conditions were modeled for a flat lunar surface with day temperature of 400 K. Solar irradiation and radiation to dark sky were included. The IEA temperature was held at 273 K (0°C), and radiator size was varied to show the difference in accommodation. (Note that results for an IEA temperature of 293 K (20°C) would be similar.)

These cases allowed comparison of the various isolation technologies by calculation of the heat contributed by the external environment to the radiator and the radiator size difference required to account for the additional heat dissipation. Overall, these cases showed that Case 1 was superior in limiting heat contribution from the environment. Case 4 allowed approximately 4W of additional heat into the system.

For LuSEE-Night, the team evaluated the relevance of the 4 W of additional dissipation to our system. The instrument dissipates (and therefore radiates) 88 W of operational heat. An additional 4 W of heat only adds 0.025 m^2 to the radiator (which is nominally 0.7 m^2). Thus, the difference in heat accommodation seems small. On the other hand, the box-in-a-box design and the SLI

construction require additional engineering and presents difficulties during integration and testing. Thus, we intend to proceed with Case 4 to provide both heritage and simplicity in our engineering and operations.

3.3.4 Design Layout

Overall component layout on the IEA is shown in Figure 3.22. The battery with peak power tracker (PPT), MEC, RFCOM, and thermal switches are mounted to a 900 mm x 900 mm base plate. As can be seen, there is excess room, and the base plate could shrink if the overall instrument shrinks. The overall size of the outer box, and therefore the IEA mounting plate, is driven by the radiator and solar panels which are still in the process of being designed. Our intent is to reduce the overall footprint as much as possible.

Figure 3.22: Component layout on the IEA showing the battery with picket fence power supply, MEC, RFCOM, and thermal switches.

The exact battery size, dimensions, weight, and mounting features have not been defined by a vendor at this time. The small box on top of the battery is the PPT. We are using an initial estimate based on discussions with vendors and assume that the final battery will be approximately the same size, shape, and weight. For this baseline design, the battery is located to the side of the mounting plate to reduce the bending stress. As the design matures, we may decide to move the battery to another location on the plate to balance weight distribution, for example closer to the center of the plate. We are also assuming that the battery vendor can make the battery housing thermally conductive and that we will be able to directly connect a thermal strap to the housing to remove heat, as shown in Figure 3.22.

3.3.5 Main Electronics Crate

The design for the Main Electronics Crate (MEC) will copy what was developed by the Space Sciences Laboratory (SSL) at the University of California, Berkeley (UCB). We will reduce project time and risk by using the proven design developed by SSL. This design is currently flying successfully on the Parker Solar Probe. Although we are making slight modifications to accommodate different circuit boards and connectors, the bulk of the design will remain intact.

The MEC, shown in the left panel of Figure 3.23 will consist of individual “slices” that are composed of frames which house individual printed circuit boards (PCBs), electromagnetic interference (EMI) shields, connectors, and vacuum vents. There will be four of these slices held together with tie rods or “skewers”, shown in the right panel of Figure 3.22. The four slices are the power distribution unit (PDU), control and data handling (C&DH), picket fence power supply (PFPS), and spectrometer. All electrical connections will be made outside of individual crates, simplifying assembly and testing. The modular design, along with outer connectors, allows individual slices to be removed or added to the stack as needed.

Figure 3.23: *Left panel:* Main Electronics Crate (MEC) showing individual slices. *Right panel:* Skewers in the Main Electronics Crate (MEC) that compress all slices.

The left panel of Figure 3.24 shows how the PCBs are mounted in each frame. Behind the PCB (not shown) is an EMI shield. The right panel of the same figure shows that when slices are stacked each PCB is protected on both front and back by EMI shields. Along with the compression placed on the frame by the tie rods, interlocking features on each frame keep slices fixed relative to each other.

Figure 3.24: *Left Panel:* Electronics board mounted in a frame. *Right Panel:* Cross-sectional view of the MEC showing alternating EMI shields (gray) and PCBs (green)

Each electronic board will be attached to frames using screws and custom inserts designed by SSL that have a Spirallock® thread which will prevent the screws from loosening. Spirallock® threads are used elsewhere in the assembly for the same reason.

The circuit boards will have a conductive ground plane on the edges which will transfer heat away from the PCB to the frame of each slice. Multiple screws, along with the Spirallock® retainers, will clamp the circuit board into thermal contact against the frame.

The MEC will be fastened to a plate which will transfer heat to the thermal switches, and the MEC and plate will be attached to the overall IEA mounting plate. The thermal gasketing material between the MEC and heat transfer plate will be Cho-Seal 1285, used previously by SSL in this application.

For the engineering model, the frames will be bare aluminum, but for the flight model, the inner walls of the frames will be black anodized, and the outer walls will be painted with black paint, Aeroglaze Z307.

Connectors on frames will be retained by custom retainers developed by UCB, shown in the left panel of Figure 3.25 . These retainers have Spirallock® tapped holes to prevent the retaining screws from loosening. The right panel of Figure 3.25 shows a vacuum vent that will be installed on each slice and allow any gasses inside to vent to space.

Figure 3.25: *Left Panel:* Custom retainer developed by UCB. Image courtesy of UCB. *Right Panel:* Image of a vacuum vent used for each slice.

We plan to make the a few minor changes to the design from SSL:

First, all of the slices on the MEC from BNL will have mounting feet, unlike the SSL MEC in which mounting feet were on every other slice. While the SSL design has flown successfully, adding mounting feet to each slice will reduce overall risk. One possible risk is the slices without feet could shift in place during the extreme vibration of launch. If this were the case, thermal contact could be reduced or lost. Adding feet will guarantee that thermal contact is maintained, and it will also result in a more mechanically robust design.

Second, we plan to simplify the design of the skewers. The original skewers designed by SSL used a key to prevent motion between the threaded rod and one of the nuts during assembly. This design required milling a slot in the end of the threaded rod, broaching a slot in the nut, adding a key, and adding a retaining screw to hold everything together. Instead, we will simply tack weld the nut to the rod to prevent rotation.

Third, the end slices on SSL were five-sided frames, meaning that there was no EMI shield which could be removed from the frame; it was part of the frame. This prevented access to the bottom of the circuit board without full disassembly. The design by BNL will use four-sided frames with removable EMI shields for all slices. This will allow better access to the underside of the PCBs and will allow us to reduce the total number of different frames.

3.3.6 Mass Budget

Table 3.1 shows the mass budget for the entire instrument, broken down by the IEA (BNL's scope) and other components (SSL and LBNL's scope). The total not-to-exceed mass is 100 kg. Currently the best estimate is 111.7 kg which exceeds the maximum by 11.7 kg. The mass was estimated for the thermal switches, miniaturized loop heat pipe assemblies, and radiator, based on the JPL models and scaled appropriately to an estimated size determined by thermal analysis done at SSL. The mass for the frame was estimated based on input from SSL. Some mass may be able to be removed from the loop heat pipe assemblies and radiator when designing the final system, as there appears to be some redundant mass between the two assemblies. If the outer box size is reduced, it will also reduce the size and mass of the IEA mounting plate. The extent that the outer box can shrink is determined by the solar panels and radiator, and we intend to reduce the size as much as possible. We also have room to reduce the mounting plate mass once we know the final design for the battery and can better optimize the plate and support points. Further analysis and refinement is needed.

Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA)	CBE Mass (kg)
Peak Poer Tracker (PPT) (On battery)	0.81
Power Distribution Unit (PDU) (Slice in MEC)	1
Digital Control Board (DCB) (Slice in MEC)	0.81
Picket Fence Power Supply (PF-PS)(Slice in MEC)	1
Spectrometer (Slice in MEC)	0.83
RFCOMM (Separate from MEC)	0.37
Inner box harness	1.5
Inner box hardware	0.05
Thermal Strap	0.21
Battery	45
Heat transfer plate, straps, gasket material	1
IEA mounting plate	7.9
Preamp (Not in IEA, but BNL scope)	0.2
Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA) Total	60.68
<hr/>	
Outer Box (SSL Scope)	CBE Mass (kg)
Lander Interface Bracket (LIB)	
Mounting feet	
Outer Box Total	15
<hr/>	
Attachments (SSL and LBNL Scope)	CBE Mass (kg)
Sci-Antenna (x4 antenna, turntable, cables)	7.8
Launch lock for turntable - frangibolt	
Launch lock for stacer - pin puller	
Solar array	5
Comm-Antenna	0.5
Thermal switches	1.2
Heat pipes and plate	6.5
Radiator	11
Multi-Layer Insulation	1
Attachment Harness	3
Attachments Total	36
<hr/>	
Totals	
Not To Exceed (NTE) (kg)	100
Current Best Estimate (CBE) (kg)	111.7

Table 3.1: Summary of mass allocation.

3.3.7 IEA Thermal Design

A thermal analysis provided by SSL compares various configurations for the inner equipment assembly. SSL analysis compares a full isolation model with eight tension cables and spacerless MLI to a model with conventional isolators and standard MLI. For the thermal analysis at BNL, the configuration and values found in Case 4, discussed in the Design Strategy section, are being used for the expected temperature range of the thermal switch.

From the analysis provided by SSL, the inner box temperature is 282.8 K (0 °C) in the day and 272.7 K (0 °C) in the night. For BNL thermal analysis, these values are references for steady-state temperature range of each thermal switch. This will be used to calculate the temperature of the MEC, RFCOM, and battery connected through an Aluminum, 6061 thermal mounting plate. Conduction from the bottom of the thermal bracket to the mounting plate, and from the battery to the mounting plate, are not included in this analysis.

Figure 3.26: *Left Panel:* Thermal Bracket without components has walls labeled as A, B, C. *Right Panel:* Thermal bracket with components shown in the flipped position.

On the inside of wall A in Figure 3.26, a J-shaped multi-row graphite fiber cable strap connects to the battery. Two thermal switches are mounted on the outside of A. The battery's thermal strap allows for flexibility and is a lightweight, thermally conductive alternative to an additional bracket. The RFCOM is mounted adjacent to A on the outside of wall B. Mounted on top of C, the bracket floor, is the bottom of the MEC. The MEC electronics heat travels to the thermal pathway leading to the bottom surface of the MEC. By using three sides of the bracket to each component, thermal pathway interference to the thermal switches is optimized for heat transfer and mass of overall system. The bracket is also an equilibrium between the components to regulate temperature.

In order to ensure good thermal conductivity, between each face of the components will be a thermally and electrically conductive silver-aluminum filled silicone gasket. The silicone outside layer provides corrosion resistance and will fill the gaps for efficient conduction.

The thermal switch provided by SSL has an expected actuation temperature of 273 K (0 °C). When the thermal switch is on, the gap is in the negative position where thermal conductivity is assumed to be 5 W/m-C. When the gap is in the positive position, the thermal switch is off and the conductance was assumed as 0.002 W/m-C. During the day, the thermal switch will be on, estimated in the highly negative position at 300 K. In the nighttime, the switch will cycle to maintain temperature at 273 K.

The Aluminum 6061 bracket to thermal switch, MEC, and thermal strap has a thermal conductivity (k) of 167 W/m-C. The thermal strap to battery has a conductance of 2.5 W/K per cable row. This thermal strap uses five rows of graphite fiber cable straps connected to the same end footing.

During day and night, the MEC and supporting electronics will be powered on with 16.7 W total. During the daytime, the battery generates 18.2 W and the RFCOM generates 8 W. The total power dissipation from radiation on all components are analyzed conservatively with a 3% heat leak from radiation.

During the daytime, the analysis assumed a thermal switch temperature of 300 K (27 °C) as an extreme condition to evaluate the thermal efficiency of the system. During the nighttime, the thermal switch was assumed to have a steady-state temperature of 273 K (0 °C).

The temperature of the MEC is expected to vary between 305 K (32 °C) in the day and 275 K (2 °C) in the night. The MEC operating temperature range is from 253 K (-20 °C) to 323 K (50 °C). The electronics temperature inside are expected to be 10 K to 15 K higher than the bottom of the MEC,

and the maximum is expected to be 320 K (47 °C). Although this is close to the maximum threshold, the conduction to the mounting plate is not considered as a thermal pathway. The next step is to encompass as many details as available for advanced thermal simulation.

A proposed battery without a heater has an operational range of 253 K (-20 °C) to 313 K (40 °C) and a maximum temperature range of 253 K (-20 °C) to 333 K (60 °C). The end of the thermal strap which connects to the battery is expected to have a 1-5 K temperature increase from the thermal switch during the day, and other areas of the battery and battery housing are expected to have a higher temperature. Further analysis is not possible without the final design of the battery.

If the thermal switch is 300 K, then a 5 K increase would bring the end of the thermal strap to 305 K, which is within the 253 K to 313 K acceptable temperature for operation, with some margin for a temperature rise between the thermal strap and other areas of the battery. The thermal switch may get above 300 K, which would cause the battery to approach its upper temperature limit. More analysis is needed. In the nighttime, the battery will still be connected to the thermal plate and heat generating components through the thermal strap and mounting plate. During the nighttime, the battery is assumed to not generate heat but the MEC will provide heat. The thermal strap connected to the battery has an expected temperature range from 273 K (0 °C) to 275 K (2 °C).

The temperature range of the RFCOM is expected to be 318 K (45 °C) to 273 K (0 °C). The information provided from SSL has not yet provided an absolute temperature range. The design will be updated based on feedback from SSL and the RFCOM vendor.

There are still uncertainties that will need to be addressed, for example, the finalized designs for the battery and the thermal strap sourced from outside vendors and the thermal switch and radiator from JPL. As the thermal analysis matures, this may drive the design considerations for these components as well. These values will change as more information becomes available for the supporting components.

3.3.8 IEA Mounting Plate Analysis

The current iteration of the design for the Inner Equipment Assembly (IEA) is a plate with the equipment mounted on top. Mounted equipment includes the battery and Peak Power Tracker (PPT), Main Electronics Crate (MEC), thermal switches, and RFCOM. A design force from 30 g of acceleration was determined, and a weight limit for the plate was initially given at 1.5 kg with a footprint of 90 X 90 cm.

Figure 3.27: Equivalent Stress Values in 30 g analysis of 25.4 mm thick aluminum plate.

A preliminary analysis of a 25.4 mm (1 in) thick aluminum plate, Figure 3.27, was completed to get an idea of the plate’s response to loads from 30 g acceleration. This was only done as a first step to verify stresses with a simple model, knowing that the weight would exceed the allotment. The solid aluminum plate performed well at 30 g. However, it weighed nearly 30 kg. The plate had stress clouds of about 30 MPa, far below the yield stress of 276 MPa, and a maximum deflection of 8.8 mm. There were a small number of high stress point outliers which can be ignored as they are artifacts of the boundary conditions.

Figure 3.28: IEA on conceptual honeycomb sandwich plate.

Following the success of the thick plate, a honeycomb sandwich plate, Figure 3.28, was designed and analyzed. The plate was comprised of a honeycomb aluminum core and aluminum sheets, with thicknesses of 20 mm and 1 mm, respectively. The 22 mm thick assembly was nearly as thick

as the solid aluminum plate but weighed only 8.25 kg. This assembly was also equipped with physical models that simulate the battery, MEC, thermal switches, and RFCOM. These physical models provide extra stability to the plate, decreasing the deflection. The densities of these features were set so that their simulated weight was 10% higher than their known values. This was to provide some margin against minor design changes, since multiple aspects of the design were converging simultaneously along with the simulations. For example, this will allow the weight of the picket fence power supply to be accounted for in the same footprint as the battery, which was not originally included when the analysis was run.

Figure 3.29: Honeycomb sandwich plate assembly stress plot.

Figure 3.30: Honeycomb-core stress plot.

Figure 3.29 and Figure 3.30 show the results of the static stress finite element analysis performed on the assembly (Figure 3.28) at 30 g acceleration. The assembly did not perform exactly as the solid aluminum plate, but it does withstand the loads of the IEA. There are a few outlier stress

points, specifically at the corners of the mounted electronics and corners of the boundary condition mounting blocks. Barring these outlier points, the stresses on the assembly do not exceed 130 MPa, and the assembly does not deflect more than 3.3 mm (less than the solid aluminum plate). The lower deflection in the honeycomb plate is attributed to using 3D modeled components on the plate, rather than simple contact areas, which added rigidity to the simulation and decreased the amount that the plate can bend. This is a closer match to how the system would behave with real components.

Certain aspects of the design are not yet known, such as the mounting conditions for the electronics and sandwich plate supports, weight of the cables, and weight of the MLI. These will affect the results of the analysis, but adding 10% margin on the masses of existing components helps to account for the components which were not directly included.

While a solid aluminum plate proves to be effective, the analysis above shows that a honeycomb plate is more efficient and can greatly reduce the weight of the assembly. Further optimization can be completed to determine the minimum necessary mass of the aluminum honeycomb plate which is more than 3.5 times lighter than the solid aluminum plate.

Another plate was also designed and analyzed. Like the original solid aluminum plate, this design is comprised of one piece of aluminum. This solid part had material removed underneath and maintained a structure that was designed to hold its rigidity, see Figure 3.31 and Figure 3.32.

Figure 3.31: IEA on machined aluminum plate.

Figure 3.32: Underside of machined aluminum plate.

The machined plate weighs 7.65 kg, compared to the 30 kg solid aluminum plate, and only deflects 2 mm under a 30 g acceleration. Like the honeycomb sandwich, this plate deflects less than the solid aluminum plate model because the included component bodies are believed to prevent some bending when compared to an empty plate with forces applied to it.

Figure 3.33: Machined plate stress analysis results.

Figure 3.34: Maximum stress location on machined plate.

As previously mentioned, the yield strength for aluminum 6061-T6 is about 276 MPa. The stress plots in Figure 3.33 and Figure 3.34 show that most of the machined plate is experiencing stress less than the yield strength. The few points with stress values greater than the yield strength have been noted and are being addressed in design changes that shore up the locations of stress concentrations. The machined aluminum plate proves to be very strong for its weight and will likely be easier to source than the honeycomb sandwich. This design will also allow us to easily add in mounting features and reinforcements to best optimize material. The design for the plate will mature as more information about the supported components becomes available.

3.3.9 Pre-amplifier Box Design

The pre-amplifiers will be mounted outside of the IEA, but they are within BNL's scope.

The current pre-amplifier design calls for four pre-amplifier assemblies, one paired with each science antenna assembly. The pre-amplifier boxes will be mounted to below the science antenna deploy unit as shown in Figure 3.35. The pre-amplifier housing will be mounted such that it is thermally isolated from the deploy unit. In this configuration, the deploy unit will limit the view for emitting and absorbing heat in the continually changing environment. Additionally, the pre-amplifier housing will be covered with multi-layer insulation. Further thermal analysis will be performed to refine this design.

Figure 3.35: Preamplifier mounting location.

The preamplifier assembly consists of a housing containing the preamplifier circuit board, two bulkhead mount SMA female connectors, and a bulkhead mount HD DSUB 15 pin connector. See Figure 3.36. One SMA connector will mate with semirigid coaxial cable routing to the antenna assembly, and the second SMA connector will mate with a semi-rigid cable which connects to the spectrometer slice in the MEC. The 15 pin DSUB connector will route to the preamplifier power supply board located in the Inner Equipment Assembly. Connectors will be fixed to the preamplifier housing using custom retainers utilizing Spirallock® tapped holes to prevent the retaining screws from loosening.

Figure 3.36: Preamplifier assembly.

3.3.10 Shipping Container

The shipping container has not yet been designed, and this effort will occur later in the project. Several years ago, BNL designed a shipping crate for part of the camera on the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST). The Inner Equipment Assembly will be roughly the same size as what was shipped for LSST, so we will have a good starting point for our design.

3.4 POWER DELIVERY

3.4.1 Overview

LuSEE-Night has to operate during the lunar night that is approximately 355h long (lunar synodic month). During this time the onboard battery will provide power to the electronics and will be gradually depleted until the next sun rise when power from the photovoltaic panel will power the electronics and recharge the battery for the next night. This process is outlined in Figure 3.37

Figure 3.37: Plot of power consumption, solar power production and charge state of the battery as a function of the lunar day/night cycle. The maximum capacity of the battery is 7000 Wh and discharges to 1000Wh during the lunar night. The solar power production is 70W at the noon peak.

The components of the power delivery subsystem are shown in Figure 2.2 and include the battery, the photovoltaic panel, its associated peak power tracker (PPT), the power distribution unit (PDU) and the low noise picket fence power supply (PFPS). The battery will provide the main bus power to the PDU unit which can route power for the various other slices of the MEC. For the startup of operations, when power is initially available, the PDU it will route power to the PFPS which in turn powers the CD&H computer to boot. Further operation is then managed from within the C&DH computer software control. The C&DH will then instruct the PDU to route power to the PFPS to provide clean power and synchronize the systems DC/DC converters from battery to PFPS. When clean power is available, the C&DH will instruct the PDU to power up the spectrometer and the antenna slice. This would be the configuration for night time operation. The battery provides telemetry to the C&DH, such that the charge and discharge current, the state of charge (SOC), and the temperature are always known and the onboard software can act accordingly.

During day the PPT will find the optimum operating point for the photovoltaic cells and provide that power to the battery where the battery built-in Battery Management System (BMS) will apportion power between the main bus and charging the battery cells. When the C&DH telemetry indicates that sufficient solar power is available it will instruct the PDU to route power to the RF-Radio for communication (see communication subsection) in addition to the battery being charged. For the corner case where the battery is too cold to be efficiently charged, power from the photovoltaic cells will be used to first heat the battery with a resistive heater and the battery will start charging once it reaches a suitable temperature. The current best estimate (CBE) for power consumption of the various components is shown in Table 3.2. During the night we expect an average power draw of 15.6 W over a duration of 384h, which is a duration of total darkness (355h) plus the extra time during dusk and dawn, where the power generated would be insufficient. During the remaining

326h the system will require an average of 25.6 W of power the electronics and the RF-radio for communication. Any surplus power generated by the photovoltaic cells will be used to charge the battery. Charging is assumed to achieve 95% efficiency. The total average power production needed during the day time is around 50 W and to achieve this around 70W of photovoltaic capacity needs to be installed. Further margin will be needed for dust and shading. Figure 3.37 shows a plot of the power consumption and production as a function of the lunar day/night cycle. If needed for thermal control (not to overheat) or for power management (insufficient solar power) the C&DH software can control the various parts of LuSEE-Night and un-power the spectrometer and preamps or power the RF-radio only when communication is expected (as shown in Figure 3.37). Using average performance data from space grade photovoltaic panel vendors LuSEE-Night will need a minimum of 0.36m² of solar cells. The exact size of the panel will be determined with margin management and more detailed simulations of LuSEE at the proposed landing site.

3.4.2 Total electrical power estimate

Subsystem power estimates are given in Table 3.2. Note that the RTG4 FPGA on the Spectrometer will be operated at a duty cycle of 50% to prevent the ~7000W-hr battery from discharging below 15% capacity over the course of a lunar night.

Component	Night Power[W]	Day Power[W]	Note
PPT	0	2	4% of power
PDU	0.1	0.1	
CD&H (DPU)	2	2	
PFPS	6	6	
SPECTR	6.9	6.9	FPGA duty factor 50%
COMM	0	8	20% duty factor assumed
Preamps	0.6	0.6	
BATTERY	0	24.2	charging efficiency 95%
TOTAL	15.6	49.8	

Table 3.2: Instrument electrical power during Night and Day operations (best estimate as of 25 July 2022).

3.4.3 Power Distribution Unit (PDU)

The PDU function is to direct/switch power to subsystems and provide telemetry of the power sources (voltage levels, currents, temperature). The PDU input power comes from the battery during normal operation, but can also be supplied from the electrical Ground Support Equipment power for ground testing. Further it can receive lander power, used to charge the battery during transit or for deployment mode. The power input is 28V unregulated.

The lander power is used for deployment of 5 launch locks. Four of them are EBAD TiNi Pin Puller P5 parts. They require 0.4A – 1.5A operational current and function time is 130 msec max @ 0.5A (23 C). The carousel lock is EBAD TiNi Frangibolt actuator FC2. The operational voltage 22-36V with current draw 0.9A@28V. The typical function time is 30 sec @28V (23 C). The selected launch lock is energized for the one-time pulsed deployment by the command from C&DH computer. For this operation lander power is directed to PFPS as well. The success/fail status will be determined by photographing the locks; decoder readings; and antenna operation.

The battery power In Lunar operation mode is directed to low EMI power supply, PFPS through two separate feeds. One feed supplies continuous operation and second feed is activated to operate motors when changing antenna positions is requested. In the daytime mode PDU supplies power to RF-COMM (Vulcan radio) in addition to PFPS. This power feed is activated by C&DH computer command. The PDU states are controlled by C&DH computer commands and control lines from the battery including a power ready signal. When power ready state is active the power can be used to energize the PFPS and the rest of the equipment.

The PDU provides telemetry, current and voltage, of the input power. It receives battery temperature values from the battery and the solar panel. These signals are buffered and passed to the C&DH computer.

3.5 COMMUNICATION

LuSEE will be stationed on the far side of the Moon. Due to Moon's tidally-locked orbit, it's angular velocity around the earth matches the angular velocity around its own axis. Consequently the Moon faces the Earth with the same hemisphere, but the entire Moon-Earth system rotates with respect to the Sun. Both near and far lunar hemispheres experience ordinary lunar "days" with a full solar cycle (time between subsequent solar transits) of about 29.5 Earth days and lunar sidereal cycle of about 27.3 Earth days (time between subsequent transits of a distant star).

This cycle defines the basic observational pattern of the LuSEE-Night experiment. We perform ultra-quiet lunar night-time observation for about 15 earth days, followed by the lunar day-time 15 earth days, during which we recharge the batteries and perform communications with the Earth. These communications will involve the download of the data as well as housekeeping information. It will also involve uploading the system configuration for the next observing run. Since there are approximately two earth weeks during this period, the results of the previous night's observation will likely influence settings and configuration for the subsequent night operation.

Because the lander will be located on the far side of the moon, the communication will necessarily be performed via the relay satellite. The current plan is to use the European Space Agency's Lunar Pathfinder Satellite³ (LPF). LPF is a first step towards ESA's ambitious Moonlight vision to create a network of communications and data relay satellites serving users worldwide. It is a dedicated mission to the moon to provide communication capabilities to assets on the far lunar side in S-band and X-band. It is currently scheduled to launch on the same rocket that will deliver CS-3 mission on which the LuSEE-Night will reside.

LPF is built by the Surrey Space Technologies SSTL and will be operated commercially. That is, most actors will have to acquire appropriate bandwidth by negotiation with SSTL. LPF will operate by default in a store-and-forward mode in which the data will be exchanged with the lunar asset at appropriate times and communicated to Earth later.

LPF will be delivered into a high elliptical inclined frozen orbit. Majority of orbits around the Moon are unstable, but a small set of orbital inclinations are naturally stable. LPF's orbit will be elliptical so that it will spend majority of the time serving the lunar southern hemisphere which is believed to be commercially more interesting.

The lander of CS-3 will also carry a Jet Propulsion Lab (JPL) user terminal which will be used to commission the LPF communication capabilities. It will be an S-band receiver system. LuSEE-Night will rely on a clone of the JPL system, using the same radio and software, but a different antenna.

³<https://bsgn.esa.int/service/lunar-pathfinder/>

Our current design involves a medium gain patch antenna located at the top of the turntable and 4W emission power. The total bandwidth will be of course dominated by the data download from the instrument to earth, since the configuration packets are rather modest in size.

To estimate the feasibility of this plan we have estimated our data needs and then compared those to the total available bandwidth. This calculation was done as follows.

The minimum estimated data transfer is as follows. If raw data are averaged in the instrument over timescales that are too long, the sky signal will be smeared, leading to a loss of information. On the other hand, if the integration is too short, we are transmitting data that is noisier than any temporal changes in signal, leading to inefficient use of bandwidth. This leads to a condition that

$$\Delta t \sim \left(\left(\frac{d \log T}{dt} \right)^2 B \right)^{-1/3}, \quad (3.5)$$

where δt is the integration time, $\frac{d \log T}{dt}$ is the logarithmic rate of change of signal due to Moon's rotation and B is the bandwidth of a bin. Using plausible assumptions this lead to $\Delta t \sim 1$ min that further leads to about 500MB of data for 15 day integration. Of course, this is an absolute minimum without any housekeeping. In practice, we want to sample at finer resolutions, add significant amounts of house-keeping data as well as raw data segments, self-subtracted power spectra, etc that will help us better understand that system performance and calibration issues. Table 3.3 describes currently envisioned data payload volumes. In short, the science requirement is that at least 3.5GB of data are transferred every lunar day. By using more aggressive lossy compression it would be possible to reduce data payload to 1GB. At data volumes below 1GB per lunar day, the science will start to become seriously impacted. On the other hand, there is almost no upper limit on how much data we can transfer that will bring some value to the project as described next.

The valuable commodity is the bandwidth to Earth rather than the actual data storage. We therefore plan to have significantly more storage than the available bandwidth. The current plan is to have 128GB of solid state storage and total daily payloads of 64GB. Each night's total payload will be available for the day following the observations and one more subsequent lunar day. The total payload will consist of a small "always-transfer" portion and further data that will be transferred upon request. For example, based on how the data looks, we might decide to download further data which are either more finely averaged in time or frequency or some other combination.

Item	Size (GB)	Comment
Main auto and cross-power spectra	1-2	16 power spectra, every 30s, 1024 spectral bins, 2 bytes per bin
Additional power spectra	1-4	self-subtracted data, outlier corrected spectra, high-res spectra
House-keeping data	0.5	200 sensors, every second at 2 bytes per reading
raw-data streams	1-2	both raw ADC samples, unaveraged raw PFB samples
Total	3.5 - 8.5	Total data per night.

Table 3.3: The total data payload size for individual lunar night.

Figure 3.38: Figure showing LPF passes over LuSEE on a representative lunar day assuming landing latitude of -10° for a medium gain antenna (case #1 described in the text). Dots on each track are separated by one minute of transit time. Dot colors show the raw bit rate calculated as the highest raw bitrate that provided more than 3dB of link margin. Useful bitrate is approximately 66% of the raw one.

To understand the total available bandwidth, we have performed the following calculation. We have assumed a nominal frozen orbit for the LPF and neglected any perturbation. We have studied two cases. In the first case the communication module is operating with 4W emitted power and a low-gain antenna. The low-gain antenna was conservatively assumed to have no gain. Nevertheless, as the satellite gets closer, the equipment is capable of switching to a higher bitrate. Following SSTL specification we assumed that raw bit rates are quantized in powers of two with the maximum bitrate of 2048Mbps and that bit rates can adapt dynamically as the satellite tracks across the sky⁴. We have then re-implemented the link margin calculation from the SSTL provided spreadsheet. This calculation takes into account various errors in pointing (the satellite antenna actively points at the asset on the Moon) and then based on the total gain and distance calculates link margin for each

⁴See Lunar Pathfinder User Manual at <https://irp-cdn.multiscreensite.com/19e31c60/files/uploaded/LunarPathfinder-UserManual-WebSite-v002-2.pdf>

Total transfer volume in GB per lunar day						
latitude	Dynamic rate			Fixed rate 85kbps		
	min	max	mean	min	max	mean
30°	8.5	15.0	11.6	1.6	3.2	2.3
20°	11.2	25.2	13.9	1.8	4.8	3.1
10°	9.8	27.2	14.2	2.0	6.0	3.7
0°	10.8	20.3	14.9	2.2	6.7	4.2
-10°	9.8	20.9	15.4	2.4	7.1	4.6
-20°	8.7	21.6	15.9	2.6	7.6	4.9
-30°	7.4	22.8	16.6	3.0	7.8	5.4
-40°	9.6	25.7	18.1	4.1	8.1	6.1
-50°	12.5	27.6	20.2	6.2	8.3	7.2
-60°	12.9	23.1	17.8	7.0	8.4	7.7
-70°	12.9	17.9	15.5	7.5	8.5	8.0

Table 3.4: Total theoretically available transfer rates from LuSEE to LPF as a function of landing latitude. Minimum and maximum vary from lunar day to lunar day due to relative orientations of LPF orbits with respect to the landing site. Three presented sets of numbers correspond to dynamic data rate and fixed data rate scenarios. We assume an elevation mask of 10°.

raw bit rate. The coded bit rate is 66% of the raw-bit rate and is the available bandwidth for data transfer. We change the rate to maintain the 3dB link margin. In the second case we simply assume 85kbps fixed transfer rate (corresponding to 128kbps raw data rate).

We assume we can transfer during the 12 central days of each lunar day. A set of tracks together with associated raw rates as plotted in Figure 3.38 for a representative lunar day. Aggregate results of this exercise are presented in the Table 3.4. We see that in all cases the total available volume exceeds our needs. Interestingly, for southern locations, the data transfers is generally higher but also varies considerably from day to day. The equator locations provide a good margin in the available bandwidth, although what fraction of the total theoretically available bandwidth will be available to us remains to be determined.

3.6 CALIBRATION

LuSEE-Night calibration involves understanding conversion of the raw data power spectra measured in ADU² units (where ADU is the natural unit of the ADC unit) into physical fluxes on the sky measured in W/m²/Hz as a function of frequency as well as precise understanding the antenna beams of our instrument. Unfortunately there is no single technique that can reliably calibrate our instrument and therefore we need to rely on a combination of techniques to achieve and cross-check our calibration vectors. This process will heavily rely on combination of electromagnetic simulations as well and pre-flight instrument characterization.

3.6.1 In-orbit Calibrator

Our best calibration vector would come from an external far-field calibrations source. In the specification for mission request for proposals we have added a "calibration service" as an optional

add-on on which the launch providers can bid. The far-field calibrator in orbit will act as a known source providing both good absolute and precise relative sky calibration as well as provide technical demonstration for future experiments. Most low moon orbits will provide a good coverage of our beam in multiple directions as well as cross linking (see for example the communication orbiter coverage as illustrated in the Figure 3.38).

Figure 3.39: Illustration of the digital calibrator concept. Calibrator emits a known digital waveform in repetition. The receiver has a copy of waveform and can detect it with high significance in cross-correlation. Other signals do not correlate in average and hence add noise, but not bias to the calibration signal.

The calibrator works by providing a known signal that is detected in cross-correlation on the receiving end. The concept is illustrated in the Figure 3.39. In practice a calibrator emits a digital waveform of length $\tau = Nr$, where r is the calibrator digital-to-analog converter sampling rate and N is the number of samples in infinite repetition. This digital form corresponds to an frequency comb spaced by $\Delta f = 1/\tau$. The waveform is generated so that each tooth of the frequency comb contains the same amount of power. On the detection end, assuming for simplicity that the sampling rate is also r , the spectrometer accumulates the vector of length N for relatively long integration time. This acts as an optimal frequency comb detector. The integration time is limited by the clock drift between the two instruments including any potential Doppler effects. The integrated signal can be FFTed and cross-correlated with the template vector to determine both the template offset as well as complex calibration response. Importantly, this operation needs to be done only after every integration and perhaps even in the post-processing, so the scheme is very light on FPGA resources. Depending on the precise coverage of orbit and the number of passes the calibrator would do this would allow us to measure the beam response along several tracks with extreme precision and in combination of EM beam modelling allow us to determine the instrument response.

The basic parameters passed to potential vendors are listed in the Table 3.6.1. These requirements are sufficient to field a successful calibration program. The details of the scheme will have to be developed once the vendor is chosen.

Service Duration	28 days
Polarizations	both linear
Orbit requirements	20 passes, twice within 10° of zenith, uniform, interlocking coverage
Ephemeris knowledge at LuSEE-Night site	alt/az to 1° , range to 10km
Received Clock stability including Doppler drift	$< 1\text{ppm}$
Waveform specification	N_X, N_Y : 1000-8000 samples sampling rate r : 100-130 MS/s
Flux density received at LuSEE-Night site	$> 10^{-22} \text{ W/m}^2/\text{Hz}$ per polarization
Received flux post-fact knowledge	$< 10\%$ over 80% of bandwidth

Table 3.5: Requirements levied on the far-field orbiting calibrator.

3.6.2 Celestial Sources

The main celestial source available is our own galaxy. Existing measurements enable approximate absolute calibration. The most precise measurements to date still come from 1970. The RAE-2 experiment [25] in orbit around the Moon and the ground based measurements of [27] provide consistent measurements with 10% absolute accuracy. These measurement will be an important cross-check against our ground-up calibration approaches.

Next class of sources is radio emission from the solar system. During the day, we will measure emission both static and time-variable from the Sun, which can be correlated against measurements of the same events by other observatories. Emission from Jupiter reaches to higher frequencies and also varies temporally at the 10% level, but its long-term average is predictable to better accuracy [37]. Jovian emission time dependence and its polarization will enable us to separate this from other effects.

We have also investigated possibility of gated detection of Crab Pulsar pulsation. Unfortunately, at these low frequencies, the pulse is dispersed well beyond the pulse duration. While it is in principle possible to do a coherent de-dispersion, we currently do not see how to do this withing limitations of our spectrometer.

3.6.3 Direct gain calibration

As a part of pre-flight instrument characterization, we plan to do a careful campaign of characterization of overall analog and digital electronic subsystem gain as a function of measured temperatures of various subsystem components across realistic temperature ranges. At percent level precision this will become a sub-dominant contribution compared to our knowledge of beam from EM simulations. This will require specialized hardware, both to source a known signal as well as ensure controlled temperature environment.

4 ASSEMBLY, INTEGRATION & TESTING

Quality assurance for LuSEE-Night includes verification and validation procedures undertaken at various points during the instrument build. The sequence is illustrated diagrammatically in Figure 4.1.

Detailed component and subsystem requirements documents will be the basis for verification testing. Tests may include functional and performance measurements. Depending on the component, both electronic and environmental (thermal, vibration) tests may be required. The first verification step, for engineering (EM) and flight model (FM) components, will be done at the subsystem teams' sites. For the EM components, these tests must be completed by the time of the Final Design Review currently scheduled for March 2023, which will coincide with a Production Readiness Review (Step 1 in Figure 4.1). The FM components are then manufactured and the component-level qualification tests of Step 1 are repeated (September 2023). At BNL, the MEC slices are then assembled and integrated and the crate is tested on the bench, and the MEC and battery are integrated into the inner mechanical box to form the IEA FM subassembly. We plan to make a temporary hookup of the IEC with preamps, rotation stage, and comms antenna and perform a functional bench test during Fall 2023 (Step 3). A pre-ship review is scheduled for January 2024, when the results of the bench test of the IEC will be reviewed. Shipment of the DOE deliverables (IEC, antennas, and rotation stage) to SSL is scheduled for March 2024, at which point the DOE MIE project is concluded.

After completion of the MIE, the full LuSEE-Night instrument is integrated with the NASA deliverables (outer enclosure with thermal management) at SSL (step 4) followed by shipment to the CLPS lander vendor. The CLPS vendor will verify that the instrument conforms to all accommodations agreed to in Appendix A, integrate LuSEE-Night and additional payloads with the lander's mechanical, electrical, and thermal systems, and perform final tests (step 5) before transport to the launch site. The completed lander will then move to the launch site and undergo final pre-launch tests (step 6). The CS-3 CLPS launch date is currently scheduled for early 2025.

It is expected that LuSEE-Night personnel will play an active role in final instrument tests at SSL, vendor, and launch sites. See the following Section for a discussion of tests planned during transit, commissioning, and early operations on the lunar surface.

Figure 4.1: Sequence of integration and test steps: (1) component test, (2) test of integrated Main Electronics Crate), (3) lashup of IEA, preamps, rotation stage, and comm antenna, (4) integration and test of full LuSEE-Night instrument, (5) integration at CLPS lander vendor, (6) pre-launch final functional test. Steps 4-6 occur after completion of the DOE MIE project in March 2024.

5 CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

5.1 LUSEE COMMISSIONING ON THE LUNAR SURFACE

On the lunar surface and shortly after landing, LuSEE requires a short period of aliveness testing. This will involve the application of LuSEE operational power by the Lander PDU.

The LuSEE internal deployment power bus shall remain safe – unpowered – during all mission phases in which deployments are not planned. That includes times when the LuSEE MEP itself is powered.

The Lander shall provide for low-latency (<1 minute latency) LuSEE telemetry and telecommands to and from earth. Telemetry data will be sent by LuSEE to the Lander and then to the Lander's MOC from which it will flow to the LuSEE SOC. The LuSEE SOC will run commissioning procedures to generate and send telecommand sequences to verify the nominal functioning of the LuSEE instrument.

5.2 DEPLOYMENTS

On the lunar surface with basic functionality verified, LuSEE requires a period for the deployment of its appendages. The LuSEE team will develop deployment procedures to use in activating and verifying nominal functioning of the instrument followed by the deployment of its appendages. These procedures will require low-latency (<1 minute latency) real-time bi-directional telemetry and telecommands between the LuSEE SOC and the LuSEE instrument.

The Lander shall facilitate the start of the LuSEE sensor deployments no later than 12 hours after landing.

Deployments will require the application of LuSEE operational power by the Lander PDU. The LuSEE internal protected deployment power bus shall be activated for the deployments, while the MEP is powered, producing telemetry, and receiving instrument commands,

LuSEE shall design and operate an internal deployment bus interface such that the five (5) LuSEE deployment circuits are protected from accidental or premature firing.

Working with the Lander's MOC, LuSEE SOC personnel will conduct deployments of the LuSEE appendages. This will involve sending low latency near-real-time command procedures to prepare for each step in the deployment process. In coordination with the Lander MOC personnel, the LuSEE team shall be responsible for sending commands to activate the internal deployment safety power bus and the individual deployment commands.

5.3 EARLY OPERATIONS

On the lunar surface, with its appendages deployed, LuSEE will enter its initial daytime operational phase. This will involve the continuous observation of the radio sky.

Telemetry data (not low latency – not real-time) will be sent by the LuSEE MEP to the Lander and eventually to the MOC from which it will flow to the LuSEE SOC.

The LuSEE SOC expects to receive telemetry data in conjunction with the Lander-earth contact schedule. Notional contact times are apt to be about 12 hours apart. The Lander shall transfer LuSEE telemetry data to the ground with minimal latency, nominally at each ground contact.

The rate at which LuSEE telemetry data are sent to the Lander C&DH can be controlled by the LuSEE SOC with ground-based telecommands. The LuSEE MEP is equipped with a large non-volatile memory such that LuSEE telemetry can be acquired and stored internally. Telemetry data is then buffered internally by the LuSEE MEP. Buffered telemetry data can then be played back at commandable bit-rates to the Lander C&DH upon command.

LuSEE SOC personnel will collect and analyze telemetry. Based on the received telemetry data itself and a pre-planned LuSEE operations schedule, LuSEE personnel will formulate daily operational plans and build command loads.

Personnel in the LuSEE SOC will provide command loads to the MOC. The MOC will eventually forward the commands to the Lander and then to the LuSEE instrument, where they will be acted upon or installed in the instrument's stored command table for later execution.

The LuSEE SOC will provide command loads in conjunction with the Lander-earth contact schedule. Notional contact times are apt to be about 12 hours apart. The Lander shall uplink LuSEE command loads with minimal latency, nominally at each ground contact.

5.4 TRANSITION TO SCIENCE OPERATIONS

As part of the first day of operations, LuSEE will transition to using its internal systems for power generation and for communications. As the sun sets at the end of the first lunar day, the Lander batteries will drain and the Lander's daytime mission will end.

Using LuSEE specific solar panels and the LuSEE internal power system, the LuSEE internal battery system will be fully charged. LuSEE will begin operations from its internal power system. LuSEE will stop its use of the Lander power system.

Using the internal LuSEE User-Terminal transceiver, telemetry data (not low latency – not real-time) will be transmitted by the LuSEE internal transceiver to the orbiting relay spacecraft and eventually to the orbiter MOC from which it will flow to the LuSEE SOC. LuSEE will stop its use of the Lander communications system.

Based on the received telemetry data itself and a pre-planned LuSEE operations schedule, LuSEE personnel will formulate daily operational plans and build command loads.

Personnel in the LuSEE SOC will provide command loads to the Orbiter MOC. Those commands will eventually be radiated to the orbiting relay spacecraft and then to the LuSEE internal transceiver on the surface where they will be acted upon or installed in the LuSEE stored command table for later execution.

LuSEE requires that, as the sun sets at the end of the first lunar day, the Lander and all of its other subsystems will permanently cease all operations. This shall include quiescing Lander subsystems throughout the lunar night. This shall include ensuring that all lunar subsystems remain inactive when the sun rises at the end of the first and all subsequent lunar nights.

5.5 SCIENCE OPERATIONS DURING LUNAR NIGHT

On the lunar surface, with its appendages deployed and operating independently from the Lander, LuSEE will enter its night operations phase. This will involve the continuous observation of the radio sky.

Having configured its antenna subsystem (in terms of theta and phi angles) during the previous

lunar day, LuSEE will remove power from its antenna actuation system.

Having received its night operations schedule and time synchronization during communication contacts during the previous lunar day, LuSEE will remove power from its User-Terminal transceiver subsystem.

LuSEE will configure itself for night operations. LuSEE will monitor operating voltages and currents throughout the night operations to ensure safe operations that maximize scientific return.

LuSEE will begin continuous observation of the radio sky. Data will be acquired throughout the lunar night. Digital signal processing will produce a stream of averaged spectral data that will be recorded in LuSEE non-volatile memory throughout the night.

As the sun rises at the start of the next lunar day, LuSEE will transition to its daytime operations.

5.6 SCIENCE OPERATIONS DURING LUNAR DAY

On the lunar surface, with its appendages deployed and operating independently from the Lander, LuSEE will enter its day operations phase. This will involve the continuous observation of the radio sky. Day-time observations will generally be of lower priority than night-time observations but will be useful in terms of instrument operations.

As the sun rises and when LuSEE power levels allow it, LuSEE will apply power to its User-Terminal transceiver subsystem. LuSEE will then answer hails from the orbiting relay spacecraft as defined by the orbiter's contact schedule. As the orbiter contact schedule allows, LuSEE will receive CCSDS telecommand data sent from the LuSEE SOC through the orbiter. The notional telecommand volume to LuSEE is expected to be small. As the orbiter contact schedule allows, LuSEE will send telemetry data to the LuSEE SOC through the orbiter. The notional telemetry to be returned through the relay spacecraft is to be 10GB per lunar cycle (28 earth days).

Based on planning and data obtained from previous night observing periods, the LuSEE SOC will send commands to configure the LuSEE antenna subsystem (in terms of theta and phi angles) during the lunar day.

Based on planning and data obtained from previous night observing periods, the LuSEE SOC will send a stored command table set of commands to be used in night operations during the following lunar night.

LuSEE will configure itself for day operations. LuSEE will monitor operating voltages and currents and battery charging throughout day-time operations to ensure safe operations that maximize scientific return.

As the sun sets at the end of the lunar day, LuSEE will transition to its night-time operations.

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